

THE NATIONAL EVOLUTIONARY SYNTHESIS CENTER ANNUAL REPORT

YEAR 10, JANUARY – SEPTEMBER 2014

Message from the Director

NESCent will close its doors on 30 June 2015. There is a great deal happening until then – many meetings and visitors, plus all the activities that go with shutting down a reasonably sized operation. There is also the likelihood that a new center will emerge focusing on evolutionary medicine, and supported by Duke University, the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, and the North Carolina State University. So even after NESCent pulls the drapes on its physical space, NESCent-sponsored activities may continue, as we transition to the new center.

I have been NESCent's director for close to 5 years. What have I enjoyed most about the job? Really, it's the huge diversity of research that has gone on, and continues to happen, that I find most stimulating. As director, a great deal of my time is taken up with routine and not-so-routine administration. But I look forward to those periods when I can attend a seminar on something I know nothing about, or when I can work with a graduate student or postdoc on research that pushes me against the boundaries of my discipline.

I like to think that this is what others find stimulating about NESCent as well. In fact, I know it's true for many who have come here, because they tell me so. The question is: will this have a lasting effect on the nature of evolutionary science? I hope it does. Quite apart from the interdisciplinary collaborations that NESCent has helped foster, I hope that we have also increased the number of people who think synthetically or, at least, value the synthetic approach. Certainly the signs are there. There are rumblings amongst the natives, and evolutionary scientists are speaking about an extended evolutionary synthesis, for instance (see the 8 October issue of *Nature* for point-counterpoint essays on this).

I am a convert to the synthesis center model. Before I came to NESCent, I knew that synthesis centers produced great research, but I was not aware of how they play a vital role in the research ecosystem. Since I've been here, I've seen firsthand how NESCent incubates good scientific ideas, how it provides opportunities to develop proofs-of-concept, how it functions to triage projects that are ready for more significant funding from those that are less mature, and how it does all this in a way that is financially efficient. It is important that funding agencies realize this. It would be a shame to lose synthesis centers. Although we are resigned to the fact that NESCent is ending, we think that it makes sense to keep funding well-functioning synthesis centers indefinitely.

Allen Rodrigo

14 October 2014

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Executive Summary

NESCent experienced an exceptionally busy year in 2014. We coordinated the organization of Evolution 2014, which was a time-consuming but, ultimately, highly successful event. We also busied ourselves with our wind-down activities and spent a great deal of time planning for what NESCent is likely to become.

The center has been granted a no-cost extension of funding through November 30, 2015. We have instituted a plan and a timeline for winding down that includes staff redeployment or reduction, data archiving, and the disposal of assets. As part of NESCent's plan for future sustainability, we have assembled a Transition Team, comprising faculty from the three partner institutions (Duke University, UNC-Chapel Hill, and N.C. State University) who are likely to lead the next incarnation of the center. The Transition Team has been tasked with working with interested faculty and senior leaders at the three universities to develop an acceptable proposal and budget for a possible center that focuses on comparative evolutionary medicine.

NESCent coordinated the organization of the Evolution 2014 conference, held at the Raleigh Convention Center from June 20 to 25, 2014. Many staff were involved in the planning and execution of the conference, which saw the second largest attendance at any Evolution conference since its inception: close to 2,000 participants, more than 1,000 talks, more than 400 posters, and an average of 13 parallel sessions each day.

In 2015, we will still have quite a full schedule of meetings, and the NESCent space will be well-occupied until we close our doors, because we will relocate our informatics team to the main building, and we will have short-term visitors and postdoctoral fellows. Additionally, we will work with the Transition Team to trial several programs that will form the suite of activities for Tri-CEM. At the end of June 2014, remaining staff will be tasked with completing all financial tasks and archiving and disposing of assets.

Over the past year, all of NESCent's core **science** activities— postdoctoral fellows, graduate fellows, long-term sabbaticals, short-term visiting scholars, working groups and catalysis meetings— have been active. We stopped accepting applications for working groups and postdoctoral fellowships in December 2012, and we stopped accepting applications for catalysis meetings and sabbaticals in December 2013, but the activities supported in the last round of proposals will carry through our no-cost extension.

In 2014, NESCent's Calls for Proposals attracted eight proposals for catalysis meetings and sabbaticals and 35 proposals for short-term visitors and graduate fellowships. This represents an intended scaling back relative to previous years. Of these 43 total proposals, 34 were assessed very favorably during our review processes and were supported. During year 10, the center will have hosted nine postdoctoral fellows, nine sabbatical scholars, one Triangle research fellow, 18 short-term visitors, 13 graduate students, and several visiting and resident scientists.

In the past four years we have introduced four targeted initiatives to jumpstart new areas of evolutionary synthesis: Evolutionary Medicine, Synthetic Biology, Evolution and the Social Sciences, and K-12 Evolution Education for Underrepresented Minorities.

We currently have seven postdoctoral scholars, three of whom will remain supported until the end of the no-cost extension and four of whose departures are staggered between now and June 2015. In addition, we will host four sabbatical scholars and an estimated 20 short-term visitors between now and June 2015. At the moment we have 32 meetings that are or will be scheduled through June 2015; these include 10 'fifth meetings' of working groups who have completed four meetings, have demonstrated exceptional productivity, and have proposed an additional meeting in response to a Call for Proposals that we issued specifically to PIs of existing or completed working groups. We also plan one more round of applications for catalysis meetings in October 2014.

NESCent continues to provide versatile, state-of-the-art **informatics** support for the center's sponsored science program and to build capacity within the evolutionary science community at large. At the same time, the NESCent has turned its attention in the past year to providing closure to its informatics commitments and ensuring that software and data assets arising from activities are appropriately managed and stewarded after the closure of the center.

Major custom informatics work in the past year includes the TraitDB web application, the Database of Phylogenies of Languages for the study of Cultural Evolution (DPLaCE), and a Fossil Calibrations Database. The recently launched NESCent Collection in the new Nature Publishing Group publication Scientific Data provides a prestigious outlet for the publication of datasets arising from sponsored science, particularly those that do not fall within the scope of a single publication. Four data descriptors are published or in press as of the end of August, and new ones are to be added to the collection on a rolling basis.

NESCent continues to host major informatics initiatives supported by external funds, including the OpenTree AVAToL project, the Dryad Digital Repository, and the Phenoscape Knowledgebase. The Informatics team held an internal hackday and anticipates being involved in two hackathons in the coming year.

Through a partnership with several other NSF BIO Centers (iPlant, iDigBio, BEACON and SESYNC), Mozilla Science Labs, and DataONE, NESCent was pleased to host the first offering of Data Carpentry (DC) in May 2014. Nurturing self-sustaining training initiatives like Data Carpentry provides another way for NESCent to make a long-lasting investment in training that will produce returns even without the center's continued involvement. Plans are being executed for continued maintenance and hosting of online databases by researchers and their institutions. When there is not a viable option for continued maintenance, we are working with scientists to archive database contents in a reusable form.

In its tenth year, NESCent has continued its **education and outreach** activities while also seeking solutions to ensure the continuation of established programs by various partners. For the fourth consecutive year, the Darwin Day Roadshow visited 14 schools in six different states and partnered for the first time with colleagues at the BEACON Center for the Study of Evolution in Action and Lehigh University. The NESCent Ambassador program ended its third and final year with trips to Trinidad, Jamaica, and Galapagos.

NESCent partnered with BEACON at the National Association of Biology Teachers (NABT) for activities including the Evolution Symposium, the Evolution Scholar Award for biology instructors, and the NABT Evolution Education Award. The Education and Outreach division also continued to run a collection of activities at the annual Society for the Advancement of Chicanos and Native Americans in Science

(SACNAS) conference and will do so again in October. NESCent also collaborated with the North Carolina Museum of Natural Sciences to host the annual Darwin Day event in February and the three-day summer workshop for 18 high school instructors from North and South Carolina in June. At the Evolution 2014, the center continued to support the Undergraduate Diversity at Evolution program and the NESCent MSI Faculty Travel Award, which funded 25 undergraduates and three faculty members from minority-serving institutions.

NESCent Academy ran or co-sponsored several short courses, three of which were in house. The center also conducted weekly seminar series, as well as a Director's Seminar Series, which brought in more diverse speakers beyond the local area.

As we enter our final year, our efforts are focused on continuing the established, successful programs and preparing a transition of the aforementioned activities with a consortium of partners (BEACON, ASN, SSB, and SSE). Plans are underway for BEACON to provide salary for an outreach director who will run most of NESCent's existing outreach programs and activities with support from the three societies.

In the past year the **communications** director wrote and distributed eight news releases highlighting published results from NESCent-sponsored projects on topics ranging from how barnyard chickens came to be, to why some species have superior smarts, to how plants evolved to cope with cold. These news releases for the 2013-2014 received more than 30,000 page views through the news service Eurekalert, and NESCent-sponsored research was featured in more than 60 articles in mainstream outlets such as *Science News*, *National Geographic*, *Science Magazine* and *Discover*. The media outlets that covered our science collectively reach millions of readers each month, a readership that no academic journal could achieve.

NESCent sponsored its final blog contest and conference travel fellowship in which evolutionary bloggers received a travel and lodging stipend to attend the annual ScienceOnline conference. In its fourth year, the journalist-in-residence program welcomed an entomologist, freelance writer and photographer from the National Museum of Natural History; a Montana newspaper staff researching evolution and climate change; and a Pakistani science journalist and multimedia producer. NESCent has issued its final call for proposals for journalists-in-residence. The deadline is December 1, 2014, and the recipient(s) would arrive in January of February 2015.

As part of the NESCent Celebration in November, the communications division is creating a special bumper issue of the quarterly newsletter. In addition to the typical contents, the double-length issue will revisit past stories and include brief summaries of the center's accomplishments over the past decade.

The **assessment** team has continued to evaluate how successfully NESCent is fulfilling its mission by applying a three-tiered system focused on people, products, and processes. For products, we focused on building accurate records of publications and grants resulting from NESCent activities and by utilizing ImpactStory to measure the usage of such publications and products. We also collaborated with an assessment working group, which will reconvene for its third meeting in December 2013. The "Science of Science" project analyzes the center's processes to improve the way the center promotes synthetic evolutionary science.

NESCent's papers accumulated 19,479 citations compared to the 13,219 citations from the same time last year. The average number of average number of coauthors per paper has continued to stay steady at a little less than four since 2009, but this past year it has increased to about five. The center continues to see an influx of new visitors and strives to maintain a 50:50 ratio of emerging to experienced scientists.

In the final year, the assessment team will concentrate its efforts on outlining a final assessment report to sum the productivity and impact of the center. We intend to publish our results and contribute to the relatively thin literature on the sociology and policy of synthetic science.

In the past year, the primary focus of the **administration** at NESCent has been to increase the visibility of working group, sabbatical scholar, and short-term visitor support as we meet the demands of the grant closure. The administrative staff was also involved in organizing the Evolution 2014 meeting both during the lead-up to the conference and at the conference itself.

Several staff members including our communications manager, IT analyst, and logistics coordinator have already left for new opportunities, and we expect more departures in the coming months. In the meantime, we continue to support the career transition of our team through a focused professional program and opportunities to participate in relevant courses, workshops, and training.

In November 2014, NESCent will host a final symposium at the Washington Duke Inn. We anticipate hosting more than 30 ongoing working group meetings, as well as several graduate students, sabbatical scholars, short-term visitors, a journalist-in-residence, and a Triangle Scholar before the center closes in June 2015. The team will also focus on archiving all print and electronic records; managing the reduction in force issues for a staff of 20; closing the physical center in July, 2015; providing final reporting in September 2015; and closing the financial grant record in November 2015.

Highlights

Education and Outreach at NESCent

NESCent's Darwin Day Roadshow program, now four years old, sent scientists and educators to 14 schools in six states, including a middle school on a Native American Indian reservation in Arizona and a school serving student-patients at a psychiatric hospital in Massachusetts. Our highly successful NESCent Ambassador program concluded its third and final year of NSF funding with ambassadorships to Trinidad, Jamaica and the Galapagos Islands. Our various travel award programs enabled 25 undergraduates and three MSI faculty to attend the Evolution Conference in NC, four high school and community college biology instructors to attend the NABT conference in Atlanta and 17 minority graduate students to participate in three NESCent Academy summer courses. We once again ran established and successful programs such as our "Evolution and Ecology at SACNAS" events, our NABT Evolution Symposium and teacher workshop, our Evolution Education Summer Workshop for High School Teachers, and our always-popular "NESCent Evolution Film Festival/Video Contest".

Scientist identifies world's biggest-ever flying bird.

A NESCent scientist has identified the fossilized remains of an extinct giant bird that could be the biggest flying bird ever found. With an estimated 20-24-foot wingspan, the creature surpassed the previous record holder — an extinct bird named *Argentavis magnificens* — and was twice as big as the Royal Albatross, the largest flying bird today. Computer simulations show that the creature's long slender wings helped it stay aloft despite its enormous size.

A new resource for studies of language and cultural evolution

NESCent has been providing software development support for a web resource to be used and maintained by members of the "Explaining cultural diversity" Working Group. The resource, called D-PLACE (a Database of Phylogenies of Languages for the study of Cultural Evolution), will map over 100 cultural features onto language phylogenies and link these to ecological and environmental variables, in order to enable investigations into the drivers of cultural change and patterns of cultural diversity. This synthetic resource will help overcome a major barrier to advances in studies of human cultural diversity, the dispersion of data across multiple disparate sources in linguistics, biogeography and anthropology.

Nearly 50 years of lemur data now available online

A 48-year archive of life history data for the world's largest and most diverse collection of endangered primates is now digital and available online. Spearheaded by NESCent scholar Sarah Zehr, the Duke Lemur Center database allows visitors to view and download data for more than 3600 animals representing 27 species of lemurs, lorises and galagos -- distant primate cousins who predate monkeys and apes -- with more data to be uploaded in the future.

Training in data skills

A Data Carpentry bootcamp was developed in collaboration with other NSF BIO Centers (<http://datacarpentry.org/>). Inspired by the popular and long-running Software Carpentry bootcamp program, it follows an open curriculum model that can be easily adapted and offered at institutions wherever there is sufficient demand and some local instructor capacity. The course is designed as a 2 day workshop for trainees with little to no prior knowledge of programming, shell scripting, or command line tools, and aims to give trainees skills in data wrangling that they can immediately use to be more

effective and productive in their work. The first bootcamp was held at NESCent on May 8-9 with four instructors and 27 learners (including students, postdocs, faculty and staff, mostly from evolution, ecology and environmental science). Demand was high; applications for the course exceeded slots available in less than 24 hours. Bootcamps have since been offered at other NSF BIO Centers, and there is strong interest in offering bootcamps at a growing list of other sites.

Data publications

While NESCent does not support the collection of new data, sponsored science projects often invest a great deal of effort in the collection, curation, and integration of existing data for meta-analysis. It has been a long standing policy of the center that data be made available for reuse by future researchers. To support that policy, we have introduced a rolling NESCent Collection in the new Nature Publishing Group publication Scientific Data. The NESCent Collection provides an outlet for the publication of uniquely valuable data in a coherent, independently citable package, carefully described with standardized metadata. All the Data Descriptors (as they are so-called by Scientific Data) are linked to preservation snapshots of the data in a form that will be reusable for years to come (e.g. in Dryad) and some are complemented by more dynamic online resources. The first Data Descriptor, from the Tree of Sex working group, was published in June. Those published so far illustrate some of the diversity of data outputs generated through NESCent-sponsored activities, including literature-based data compilations, the results from long-term experimental and observational program, and digitized historic records (<http://www.nature.com/sdata/collections/nescent>).

1. Center Wide Activities

2014 was an exceptionally busy year for the Center. This year, we coordinated the organization of Evolution 2014 in June. This was a time-consuming but, ultimately, highly successful event. We also busied ourselves with our wind-down activities. Finally, in the midst of all this, we spent a great deal of time planning for what NESCent is likely to become. All these activities are detailed below.

1.1 2014 Activities

1.1.1 *Evolution 2014*

NESCent coordinated the organization of the Evolution 2014 conference, held at the Raleigh Convention Center from 20 – 25 June 2014. Many staff were involved in the planning and execution of the conference which, this year, saw the second largest attendance at any Evolution conference since its inception: there were close to 2000 participants, more than 1000 talks, 400+ posters, and an average of 13 parallel sessions each day.

Some of the highlights of the meeting included the Stephen Jay Gould Award Lecture by Professor Steven Jones, the Women in Science Workshop, the NESCent Film Festival, the NESCent Symposium, and the final social evening at the North Carolina Museum of Natural Sciences. Participants were very pleased with the meeting, with some calling it the best Evolution conference they had every attended.

1.1.3 *Winding Down*

We have received notification that NESCent will have a no-cost extension of funding until 30 Nov 2015. With this in mind, we have made the decision to close the doors to NESCent's physical space on 30 June 2015, so that there is time to complete all administrative, operational and logistic tasks associated with winding down the grant.

As part of this process, we have instituted a plan and a timeline for winding down that includes staff redeployment or reduction, data archiving, and the disposal of assets. All staff have been informed of their employment end dates. We are in the process of auditing NESCent's digital resources to identify those that need to remain accessible after the close-out of the grant. We are also identifying digital archives for NESCent data, and we have located physical space for NESCent paper records and documents.

1.1.2 *NESCent's Transition Team*

As part of NESCent's plan for future sustainability, we have assembled a Transition Team, comprising faculty from the three partner institutions who are likely to lead the next incarnation of the center. The Team is chaired by Dr. Charles Nunn, from the Evolutionary Anthropology Department at Duke University. The Transition Team has been tasked with working with interested faculty and senior leaders at the three institutions to develop an acceptable proposal and budget for a possible center.

The Transition Team has been meeting since February 2014 to work on this, and very early on, strong support emerged for a center that focuses on comparative and evolutionary medicine. Such a center would be strategically important to the partner institutions. Both Duke and the University of North

Carolina at Chapel Hill have medical schools. North Carolina State University has a veterinary school and has identified OneHealth as a focal research program.

The tentative name for the center is the Triangle Comparative and Evolutionary Medicine Center (TriCEM). Discussions with the provosts and other senior members of the three institutions have been very positive, and we are more optimistic than we have been in the past that TriCEM will be seen as the appropriate vehicle for evolutionary science in the region, and one that should be supported.

As part of NESCent's transition plans, we will use some of the funds during our no-cost extension to pave the way for the new center. Thus, we will support meetings, workshops, and fellowships, aimed at Triangle researchers, modeled on the intended programmatic repertoire of TriCEM.

1.1.4 NESCent Celebration Symposium

In November 2014, NESCent will hold a symposium to celebrate its time as a center, and to introduce the community to what comes next. We have invited all previous members of our Advisory Boards, our various committees, NSF program officers, and some of our most active participants. The program will include a look back at some of the successes of NESCent, and to the future, with a section of the program dedicated to comparative and evolutionary medicine.

1.2 2015 Plans

In 2015, we begin our final stage of winding the center down. We will still have quite a full schedule of meetings, and the NESCent space will be well-occupied until we close our doors, because we will be relocating our informatics team to the main building, and we will have short-term visitors and postdoctoral fellows.

Additionally, we will work with the Transition Team to trial several programs that will form the suite of activities for TriCEM.

At the end of June 2015, remaining staff will be tasked with completing all financial tasks, archiving and disposal of assets.

2. Science and Synthesis

During 2013-2014, NESCent's science activities remained vibrant and diverse. All of our core science programs - postdoctoral fellows, graduate fellows, long-term sabbaticals, short-term visiting scholars, working groups and catalysis meetings – have been active in the past year. We stopped accepting applications for working groups and postdoctoral fellowships in Dec 2012, and we stopped accepting applications for catalysis meetings and sabbaticals in Dec 2013, but the activities supported in the last round of proposals will carry through our No Cost Extension. Thus, we are continuing to enable NESCent-supported scientists to tackle many important evolutionary problems using synthetic methods, and our in-house community remains a fertile environment for research that allows diverse scientists to identify common interests and stimulate new collaborations. In addition, we are still accepting short-term visitor applications on a quarterly basis and will continue to do so for one more round in order to ensure that the resident community remains vibrant.

In addition to these core activities, an important focus of NESCent's science and synthesis team has been facilitating the transition that we anticipate NESCent will make from a national synthesis center with a broad focus on evolutionary science to a more modestly sized center with a disciplinary focus on evolutionary and comparative medicine. These transitional science activities are described in Section 1.

The science done at NESCent continues to have a high impact within the scientific community; NESCent-sponsored science continues to often be published in high-impact journals, and NESCent's h-index (a metric reflecting citation frequency), currently at 69, is still climbing (see "Assessment" section). In addition, NESCent's "news room" (see "Communications" section) worked hard through the year to facilitate media outreach, with the result that NESCent science reached the general public as well as the scientific community. The following are just a few examples of successful science stories from NESCent activities this year:

- [Scientists pinpoint the origins of human influence on everything from chickens to chili peppers](#) (April 2014). Featuring the NESCent Catalysis Meeting 'Domestication as an evolutionary phenomenon: expanding the synthesis', organized by Greger Larson, Michael Purugganan, Dolores Piperno, Robin Allaby, and Dorian Fuller. This story was also picked up by *Nature*, *Science Friday* and *Ars Technica*.
- [Overriding their animal impulses](#) (April 2014). Featuring the NESCent working group 'How does cognition evolve?' led by Charles Nunn and Brian Hare. Picked up by the *New York Times*, *National Geographic*, and the National Science Foundation's daily news feed.
- [A newly declared species may be the largest flying bird ever to live](#) (July 2014). Featuring NESCent Postdoctoral Fellow Dan Ksepka.
- [Scientists unlock the secret to prairie dogs' social networks to save them](#) (August 2014). Featuring NESCent Postdoctoral Alumna Jennifer Verdolin.
- [Project to size ocean giants melds marine science with social media](#) (Dec 2013). Featuring

Craig McClain, NESCent Assistant Director for Science.

2.1 2014 Activities

In 2014, NESCent's Calls for Proposals attracted 8 proposals for Catalysis Meetings and Sabbaticals, and 35 proposals for short-term visitors and graduate fellowships. This represents an intended scaling back relative to previous years. Of these 43 total proposals, 34 were assessed very favorably during our review processes and were supported (see Appendices for summary). The complete list of NESCent scientific projects funded in year 10 is given in the Appendices.

In the aggregate as of September 15th 2014, NESCent supported 32 scientific meetings in 2014 (20 Working Group meetings and 12 Catalysis meetings), involving 625 visitors. A complete list of meetings at NESCent in year 10 is given in the Appendices.

2.1.1 The NESCent In-house Community and Postdoctoral Development

We have maintained a vibrant and collegial community of in-house scientists, although the in-house community has certainly begun to experience the loss of membership we anticipated as we headed into year 10. During year 10, the Center will have hosted 9 postdoctoral fellows, 9 sabbatical scholars, 1 Triangle research fellow, 18 short-term visitors, 13 graduate students, and several visiting and resident scientists. Our weekly Brown Bag Lunch seminar series and Journal Club meetings remain lively touchstones for our resident community. As always, each postdoctoral fellow has a formal mentor (identified after an initial meeting with a mentoring committee to discuss the postdoctoral fellow's research plans, NESCent expectations, local and other resources) and has developed a written mentoring plan vetted by the NESCent mentor and the Associate and Assistant Directors of Science.

In addition, we run a postdoctoral professional development program that, this year, included the Postdoctoral Professional Development Seminar Series throughout the year. To present this seminar series we draw on the resident community of NESCent senior scientist (sabbatical scholars and other residents) as well as on the larger community of scientists in the Triangle, with strong participation from the three partner institutions (Duke, UNC-CH and NCSU). Recent topics have included "Teach for the Reach: Designing an Evolutionary Biology course for non-STEM majors", "Negotiating Your First Faculty Position", "Science publishing, data archiving and peer review", "Communicating Science to the Public", "Social Media/Networking at Work: Online Harassment and Bullying", "Social Media for Scientists" and "Writing Letters of Recommendation".

2.1.2 Targeted Initiatives

In the past four years we have introduced four targeted initiatives to jumpstart new areas of evolutionary synthesis: Evolutionary Medicine, Synthetic Biology, Evolution and the Social Sciences, and K-12 Evolution Education for Underrepresented Minorities.

We have conducted several activities in 2014 to further our four targeted initiatives.

- The Working Group entitled "Infusing Medical Education with Evolutionary Thinking" is an interdisciplinary, international, and intergenerational Working Group of physicians, scientists, educators, and students focused on designing curricula for medical education. The group's goals are to (i) define core competencies in evolutionary biology for physicians and other health professionals,

- (ii) design model curricula and learning experiences that can advance evolutionary education for health professionals, and (iii) provide open access to these resources and disseminate them.
- The Working Group entitled “The Perils of Being Bipedal: an Evolutionary Perspective on Human Musculoskeletal Disorders” is focused on teaching evolutionary thinking to medical students through the charismatic subject of our uniquely human stature and gait. This group will (i) develop and implement a model curriculum, (ii) create a website with course materials and supporting information, and (iii) publish an edited volume of papers on human musculoskeletal disorders.
 - The Working Group entitled “Learning Evolution from the Fossil Record: K-12 Explorations in Deep Time” brings together paleontologists, K-12 science education specialists, and museum education staff. They are in the midst of designing and delivering innovative programming that uses fossils to engage students in explorations of evolutionary concepts. In the proposed program, undergraduate and graduate students who are themselves under-represented minorities will serve as facilitators and mentors.
 - The Working Group “Genetics and Genealogy: Teaching Evolution and Human Diversity to Middle School Students” continues to meet and is developing a curriculum for a summer-camp program for middle school students. During this summer camp experience, tentatively entitled “The Peopling of the World and Me!”, students will investigate their own personal history using the tools of biology (genetics and DNA) and history (personal genealogy and family history).
 - The Working Group “Explaining cultural diversity: A new evolutionary synthesis” seeks to link data from multiple disparate sources in linguistics, biogeography and anthropology. The group is creating D-PLACE (a Database of Phylogenies of Languages for the study of Cultural Evolution), a publicly available and expandable web-portal that will map over 100 cultural features onto language phylogenies and link these to ecological and environmental variables, empowering a whole new line of investigation into the drivers of cultural change and patterns of cultural diversity.

2.1.3 Meeting enhancement

We continue to disseminate our highly detailed Best Practices document (produced in year 7, first deployed in year 8) to all group leaders, with encouragement to seek assistance and input on planning and running meetings.

2.2 2015 Plans

For the upcoming year, our major goal is to maintain a vital resident community until NESCent’s doors close in June 2015. It’s a priority for us to avoid a sense of lost momentum; we aim for minimal ‘tapering off’. We currently have 7 postdoctoral scholars, 3 of whom will remain supported until the end of the no-cost extension and 4 of whose departures are staggered between now and June 2015. In addition, we will host 4 sabbatical scholars and an estimated 20 short term visitors between now and June 2015. At the moment we have 32 meetings that are or will be scheduled through June 2015; these include 10 ‘fifth meetings’ of working groups who have completed four meetings, have demonstrated exceptional productivity, and have proposed an additional meeting in response to a Call For Proposals that we issued specifically to PIs of existing or completed Working Groups. We also plan one more round of applications for Catalysis Meetings in October 2014. From the perspective of the quality and quantity of proposals we are receiving, NESCent remains a key resource for the evolutionary community; high quality work will continue to be produced in the last year of our core funding and through our transition to the next phase of the center.

3. Informatics

NESCent continues to provide versatile, state-of-the-art informatics support for the center's sponsored science program and to build capacity within the evolutionary science community at large. At the same time, NESCent has turned its attention in the past year to providing closure to its informatics commitments and ensuring that software and data assets arising from center activities are appropriately managed and stewarded after the closure of the center.

3.1 2014 Activities

3.1.1 Support for sponsored science

Informatics support at NESCent takes many forms, from provision of basic collaboration tools (e.g. mailing lists, project wikis), to access to high-performance computing on the Duke Shared Cluster Resource (DSCR), to consultations, to software developer effort on projects that require custom tool development. Considerable effort has been given this past year to project documentation, so that future developers will be able to build, deploy, and use custom applications developed by NESCent. To the same end, effort has been invested in developing virtual machines, cloud deployment processes, and Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) for major custom applications. In the past year, we also have made a push to catalog the software and data products arising not only from sponsored science, but also other center projects such as hackathons, Google Summer of Code internships, and externally funded informatics projects on which some NESCent staff were employed. These can be seen on NESCent's Products page (<http://nescent.org/science/products.php>) by selecting Software and Datasets.

3.1.2 Custom support projects

Major custom informatics support effort in the past year include the following.

Collaborative compilation of biological trait data

NESCent has continued to develop the TraitDB web application, designed to assist our sponsored scientists to collaboratively compile trait data (<http://traitdb-dev.nescent.org>). The application handles data upload, validation, search and download. This had already been deployed to support the needs of the Tree of Sex and Social Traits working groups, and in the past year its use was extended to meet the needs of the Baker's Law working group. We are currently reaching out to other NSF BIO Synthesis Centers and external groups that may be interested in further development and use of the tool.

A database for the evolution of language and culture

The Database of Phylogenies of Languages for the study of Cultural Evolution (DPLaCE) is a web resource is designed with the Explaining Cultural Diversity working group to support investigations into the drivers of human cultural change and patterns of cultural diversity, with special attention to the role of language. This project is described more fully under Highlights.

Making fossil calibrations more robust

A Fossil Calibrations Database has been developed together with the Synthesizing and Databasing Fossil Calibrations Working Group. This unique resource should greatly expand the evidence base for the fossil calibrations that are essential for dating events in the history of life. It will be maintained by the journal *Palaeontologia Electronica*, and continually updated by community contributions through a special publication track for fossil calibration reports. Publications describing the resource are underway and it

is expected to go live in preparation for a debut at the 2014 Society for Vertebrate Paleontology conference.

Ensuring valuable research data is available for reuse

The recently launched NESCent Collection (<http://www.nature.com/sdata/collections/nescent>) in the new Nature Publishing Group publication Scientific Data provides a prestigious outlet for the publication of datasets arising from sponsored science, particularly those that do not fall within the scope of a single publication. Four data descriptors are published or in press as of the end of August 2014 (Conner et al. 2014, Plooij et al. 2014, The Tree of Sex Consortium 2014, Zehr et al. 2014) and new ones are to be added to the collection on a rolling basis. The NESCent Collection is described more fully under Highlights, and in a special commentary in Scientific Data by the collection's editors, T. Vision and K. Cranston (Vision and Cranston 2014)

3.1.3 Human capacity building: the Data Carpentry bootcamp

Through a partnership with several other NSF BIO Centers (iPlant, iDigBio, BEACON and SESYNC), Mozilla Science Labs, and DataONE, NESCent was pleased to host the first offering of Data Carpentry (DC) in May 2014. DC is a “nomadic” hands-on short course for researchers (of all ages) on basic concepts, skills, and tools for working with data - helping them to “get more done in less time, and with less pain.” The concept has proven popular, and there has been high demand at other institutions to offer similar bootcamps, using a mix of experienced and new instructors and adopting the open curricular materials. See <http://datacarpentry.org> for more information, and also the Highlights section.

The successful Evolution 2014 Meetings were a major effort on the part of many staff at the center, informatics staff included. One innovative experiment spearheaded by the informatics staff was conceived to assist the program committee in optimizing the schedule of talks and posters for the conference. Phenoscape postdoc Prashanti Manda devised methodology for clustering related talks into topically distinct parallel sessions, based on text analysis of the titles and abstracts provided by all the presenters. The computationally generated program was used for the poster session without modification, and used for the talks to varying degrees among sessions. A description and evaluation of the methodology is currently being written up for publication.

3.1.4 Synergies with externally funded projects

NESCent continues to host a number of major informatics initiatives supported by external funds, including the OpenTree AVAToL project, the Dryad Digital Repository, and the Phenoscape Knowledgebase. One benefit of hosting these projects at the center is the opportunity to take advantage of synergies with core funded activities. NESCent held an internal hackday to improve the interoperability of the sophisticated taxonomy synthesis tool developed by OpenTree, which shows great promise to be of use by other projects at NESCent and beyond. Ontology expertise from Phenoscape was used to improve the Mammalian Feeding System database (an externally funded project that began as a NESCent working group) and tapping that expertise was also the primary objective of NESCent Short-Term Visitor Jessica Kissinger. The Dryad Digital Repository is the preservation archive for much of the published data arising from NESCent sponsored science, and is a central partner in the NESCent Collection of publications in the new Scientific Data journal.

3.2 2015 Plans

During the remainder of this year and into the no-cost extension period, most of the effort will be expended in wrapping up ongoing commitments, planning for the graceful closure of the center and the archiving of its assets for future scholars. Still, custom support will continue for a number of sponsored science projects as they have their final meetings and collaborate on their research outputs. Also, NESCent is hosting or contributing to a number of human capacity building activities that will continue to provide returns long after the center closes its doors.

3.2.1 Human capacity-building: hackathons and training initiatives

Hackathons allow NESCent to nurture a community of software developers that will develop and maintain shared evoinformatics resources without continued direct involvement of the Center. We anticipate being involved in two hackathons in the coming year. The first is the Tree-for-all phyloinformatics hackathon, scheduled for September in Ann Arbor, jointly organized by the OpenTree and Arbor AVAToL projects, and the Hackathons, Interoperability, Phylogenies (HIP) NESCent working group (Stoltzfus et al. 2013). The second will be a long-deferred hackathon to improve the population genetics resources available within the R statistical language, currently planned to be held at NESCent in March 2015, and under the direction of an organizing committee that includes Hilmar Lapp (NESCent), Thibaut Jombart (Imperial College London), Stéphanie Manel (U. Aix-Marseille), Giovanni Montana (Imperial College London), Emmanuel Paradis (U. Montpellier), Bastian Pfeifer (U. Leipzig), and Gregory Warnes (U. Rochester).

Nurturing self-sustaining training initiatives like Data Carpentry provides another way for NESCent to make a long-lasting investment in training that will produce returns even without the center's continued involvement. In addition to participating as instructors for Data Carpentry bootcamps, in late 2014 NESCent will also be involved in a workshop to develop online curricular materials in Reproducible Science. This is supported in part through a funding supplement to BEACON, and is led by a steering committee that includes Karen Cranston (NESCent), Francois Michonneau (U. Florida), Sophie Kay (Kershaw) (U. Oxford), Hilmar Lapp (NESCent), Ciera Martinez (UC Davis), Sheila Miguez (Columbia), Matt Pennell (U. Idaho) and Tracy Teal (Michigan State). The aim is to develop materials that can be used by courses such as Software and Data Carpentry and that impart practical knowledge in the practices, tools, and resources for reproducible science available to biologists doing computational work. The online resources to be developed will build upon those begun at an rOpenSci hackathon (<http://ropensci.github.io/reproducibility-guide/>).

3.2.2 Stewardship of NESCent's digital assets

A major ongoing effort that will continue through June 2015 is ensuring that the digital assets of the center are managed after the doors officially close. There are several categories of assets. For one, the extensive administrative information about NESCent's programs and activities that has been used to prepare Annual Reports is maintained in a database, which will be archived with Duke University Libraries. Two, NESCent has been undertaking a comprehensive inventory of data and software outputs generated from projects in sponsored science, education & outreach (e.g. NESCent Academy), and informatics (e.g. hackathons, Google Summer of Code, externally funded projects, education & outreach activities). Staff will continue to work diligently with past and present sponsored scientists to ensure that datasets and software that fall under the NESCent Data, Software and Publication Policy are being preserved and made available in a manner consistent with that policy. Plans are being executed for continued maintenance and hosting of online databases by researchers and their institutions. When there is not a viable option for continued maintenance, we are working with scientists to archive

database contents in a reusable form. For several years, we have deliberately moved many of our digital resources (such as project wikis) to external hosts, so that they may continue without center upkeep. Where necessary, we will distribute to PIs collaboratively created text and multimedia content, either for their private records, or to be publicly hosted by another party (institution, or service provider). The intention is that, if any digital assets do not get preserved in a useful form, the choice is a deliberate one and not due to negligence, and that the sponsored scientists be party to the decisions that are made.

4. Education and Outreach

In NESCent's tenth and final full year of NSF funding our two main priorities for Education and Outreach have been:

1. Continue the established, successful activities that have been developed and implemented over the preceding nine years.
2. Aggressively seek solutions to ensure the continuation of our established education/outreach programs by the various partners and collaborators with whom we've worked over the years.

A number of our education/outreach programs have established a *brand identity* and we believe it is important that these programs continue beyond NESCent's 10-year NSF funding period, so that the education community and the general public can continue to benefit from them.

4.1 2014 Activities

As we have done in previous years, we summarize these activities most effectively in the context of the *five pillars* of NESCent Education/Outreach:

1. Outreach to the Education Community
2. Outreach to the General Public
3. Outreach to Underrepresented Minorities
4. Outreach to International Science and Education Communities
5. "Inreach" to the Science Community

4.1.1 Outreach to the Education Community

For the fourth consecutive year, NESCent's Darwin Day Roadshow (roadshow.nescent.org) program sent teams of NESCent scientists/educators to K-12 institutions in small, rural communities around the country to celebrate Charles Darwin's birthday with talks about evolution research being conducted at NESCent, and about careers in science. This year, we visited 14 schools in six different states (AL, AZ, MA, MI, PA, and RI). The visits were conducted by 11 different scientists, including five graduate students, one postdoc and one NESCent sabbatical scholar. We also partnered for the first time with colleagues at the BEACON Center for the Study of Evolution in Action (Michigan State University) and Lehigh University, who conducted visits in Michigan and Pennsylvania, respectively. Highlights included visits to Baboquivari Middle School (a Native American school in Sells, AZ), Arlington School (a school serving patients/students at McLean Psychiatric Hospital in Belmont, MA), and Auburn University Montgomery (which hosted several hundred students from multiple Montgomery, AL-area high schools for a day-long celebration of Darwin and science careers).

For the second year in a row, we partnered with BEACON on our annual Evolution Symposium organized as part of the National Association of Biology Teachers (NABT) annual conference. This year, it was held in Atlanta, GA on Nov. 22nd, 2013, and was entitled "Wallace, Islands and Biogeography: 100 Years Later". The symposium marked the 100th anniversary of Alfred Russel Wallace's death by examining his legacy in evolution. As always, our symposium was complimented by a hands-on workshop intended to

provide teachers with classroom resources and activities to introduce the topic of the symposium to their students.

For the second year in a row, we conducted the “NESCent Evolution Scholar Award” program at the NABT conference. This is a travel award program to send motivated and enthusiastic biology instructors (from both high schools and community colleges) to the NABT conference to acquire new evolutionary knowledge which they can then share with their students (through classroom activities) and colleagues (through professional development activities). This year, we welcomed BEACON as a partner, enabling us to double the number of travel awards to four (two high school teachers and two community college instructors).

NESCent continued our co-sponsorship of the NABT Evolution Education Award, along with BEACON and BSCS. The past year’s winner was Paul Strode (Fairview High School, Boulder, CO).

We once again delivered our annual three-day summer workshop for 18 high school instructors from North and South Carolina. For the second year in a row, we partnered with Dr. Jason Cryan at the North Carolina Museum of Natural Sciences. We also included colleagues from the Howard Hughes Medical Institute (HHMI), who led sessions on evolution education activities and distributed copious classroom resources from their BioInteractive collection.

4.1.2 Outreach to the General Public

The highlight of our outreach efforts for the general public continued to be the annual Darwin Day event we cofounded and co-sponsor with the North Carolina Museum of Natural Sciences. This day-long event attracted several thousand visitors to the museum on Feb. 15th, 2014. NESCent made arrangements to provide the keynote speaker (Dr. Ed Scholes from the Cornell Lab of Ornithology, who unfortunately got stuck in Ithaca, NY due to a winter storm at the last minute and was ultimately unable to attend) and ran several interactive stations and booths. NESCent also sponsored or co-sponsored several other evolution-related talks for the general public, many in partnership with the NC Museum of Natural Sciences.

4.1.3 Outreach to Underrepresented Minorities

We continued to organize and run a collection of evolution outreach activities at the annual SACNAS (Society for the Advancement of Chicanos and Native Americans in Science) conference. This was the eighth year we have run “Evolution and Ecology at SACNAS”, and NESCent continues to be the primary organizer of these events, with co-sponsorship from NCEAS, NIMBioS, SSE, and AIBS. As always, NESCent postdocs were involved as symposium speakers and mentors to minority undergraduates attending the conference. We will run these activities once again at the October, 2014 SACNAS Conference in Los Angeles, CA. In the spring of 2014 we received an Outreach and Education Grant from the Paleontological Society to support a field trip to the Page Museum/La Brea Tar Pits, so this will be a highlight of this year’s SACNAS activities.

We once again collaborated with Scott Edwards (Harvard) and Rich Kliman (Cedar Crest College) on the *Undergraduate Diversity at Evolution* program, which sends undergraduates to the annual Evolution (SSE/SSB/ASN) conference and provides them with mentoring and professional development while there. For the third year in a row, NESCent assumed full financial responsibility and organizational

oversight for the program, which brought 25 undergraduates (most of them from underrepresented minority groups) to Raleigh, NC. We are currently working on a proposal to be submitted to the NSF to secure sustainability funding for this program beyond 2015.

We continued the *NESCent MSI Faculty Travel Award* program, as well, by sending three faculty members from minority serving institutions to the Evolution 2014 Conference in Raleigh, NC to present original research, and mentor diverse undergraduates. This year's winners were Drs. Mary McKenna (Howard University), Florentine Riquet (Brooklyn College) and Tom Backman (Northwest Indian College).

Seventeen travel awards were given to students from underrepresented minority groups to participate in short courses and workshops offered by the NESCent Academy (see "Inreach").

4.1.4 Outreach to International Science and Education Communities

The NESCent Ambassador program (ambassadors.nescent.org) ended its third and final year of NSF funding with three very successful ambassadorships:

Trinidad (Oct. 2013) – As a follow-up to the November, 2011 trip to the Caribbean (which included Jamaica, Trinidad, Barbados and Belize), a team consisting of Drs. Jory Weintraub (NESCent Asst. Director of Education & Outreach, and NESCent Ambassador program manager), Courtney Fitzpatrick (NESCent postdoctoral fellow) and Sarah Fitzpatrick (Colorado State University doctoral candidate) returned to Trinidad. There, they conducted a two-day workshop ("Understanding and Teaching Evolution" - <http://www.nescent.org/eog/Trinidad2013>) for over 75 high school science instructors from Trinidad and Tobago (representing the vast majority of all high school biology instructors from that country). They also spent four days traveling to schools throughout Trinidad, giving presentations on evolution and science careers to Trinidadian high school students.

Jamaica (Nov. 2013) – As a follow-up to the November, 2011 trip to the Caribbean (which included Jamaica, Trinidad, Barbados and Belize), a team consisting of Drs. Jory Weintraub (NESCent Asst. Director of Education & Outreach, and NESCent Ambassador program manager), Fabricia Nascimento (NESCent postdoctoral fellow) and Elvis Nuñez (Manu Kai Educational Services and the Caribbean Examination Council and long-time Ambassador collaborator) returned to Jamaica. There, they conducted two two-day workshops ("Understanding and Teaching Evolution" - <http://www.nescent.org/eog/Jamaica2013>) for approximately 50 high school science instructors from all across Jamaica (representing the vast majority of all high school biology instructors from that country). One workshop was conducted in Kingston and the other in Montego Bay, representing the two biggest cities in Jamaica and on opposite sides of the island, to maximize impact of the ambassadorship. They also spent one day visiting two high schools in Kingston and a second day at Denbigh High School in May Pen, Jamaica (a small, rural community about one hour west of Kingston), giving presentations on evolution and science careers to Jamaican high school students.

Galapagos (Jan. 2014) – As part of a newly-established collaboration with Dr. Richard Knab and the Galapagos Conservancy, a team of four ambassadors traveled to the island of Santa Cruz in the Galapagos Islands. The team consisted of Drs. Jory Weintraub (NESCent Asst. Director, Education & Outreach) and Jonathan Lombard (NESCent postdoctoral fellow), Elvis Nuñez (Manu Kai Educational Services) and Sarah Cohn (NESCent Outreach Associate, and a veteran of the June 2012

Ambassadorship to the Galapagos). During the week on Santa Cruz, two days were spent giving presentations to Galapagos Naturalist Guides (employed by the Darwin Research Station) on evolution and island biogeography, and three days were spent working with students and teachers at the Tomas de Berlanga K-12 school (an educational partner of the Galapagos Conservancy). Hands-on evolution education activities were run with elementary school students, and interactive presentations on evolution were delivered to middle and high school students. All ~ 20 members of the schools faculty participated in a professional development session on “Effective, Engaging, Interactive Science Education.”

4.1.5 “Inreach” to the Science Community

The *NESCent Academy* (academy.nescent.org) once again ran or co-sponsored several short courses to the evolutionary science community. This year’s offerings included:

1. Next-Generation Sequencing Data for Phylogenetics and Phylogeography
2. Paleobiological and Phylogenetic Approaches to Macroevolution
3. Phylogenetic Analysis Using RevBayes
4. Evolutionary Quantitative Genetics (co-sponsored with National Institute for Mathematical and Biological Synthesis)
5. Workshop on Quantitative Evolutionary Biology (offered at the [Nesin Foundation Mathematics Village](#) in Turkey)

We continued to organize and conduct a weekly seminar series for in-house scientists and invited speakers from the local (NC Triangle) area. We also continued the “NESCent Director’s Seminar Series” to bring in more diverse speakers from outside the Triangle area to NESCent.

We received over 30 entries for the fourth annual “NESCent Evolution Video Contest” (filmfestival.nescent.org), which was held at the Evolution Societies meeting in Raleigh, NC.

4.2 2015 Plans

As we enter our final year, our efforts are focused on two objectives:

- A. Continue to operate the established, successful programs described above, including:
 - October, 2014 – Evolution and Outreach at SACNAS (Los Angeles, CA)
 - November, 2014 – NABT Evolution Symposium and Teacher Workshop, NESCent Evolution Scholar travel award program (Cleveland, OH)
 - February, 2015 – Darwin Day Roadshow and “Darwin Day at NC Museum of Natural Sciences”
 - June, 2015 – Undergraduate Diversity at Evolution, NESCent MSI Faculty Travel Award, Evolution Education Workshop for High School Teachers
- B. Prepare for a transition of NESCent’s education and outreach programs to a consortium of partners (BEACON, ASN, SSB and SSE) – Plans are underway for BEACON to provide salary for an Outreach Director who will run most/all of NESCent’s existing outreach programs and activities, with support from a consortium of the three societies. This transition should be seamless, so that there will be no disruption of operation of these programs when NESCent closes its doors in June of 2015.

We are pleased that the recently agreed-upon transition of our many successful education and outreach programs and activities from NESCent to BEACON will enable us to continue to impact students, teachers and the general public, both nationally and internationally. Not only does this benefit the many audiences we've been serving over the last 10 years, but given that both NESCent and BEACON are NSF-supported centers, it represents an important leveraging of NSF funds.

As we approach the anticipated shut-down of NESCent's facilities at the end of June, 2015, we intend to allocate any remaining, unspent education/outreach funds towards support of education/outreach initiatives associated with the proposed Triangle Comparative and Evolutionary Medicine (TriCEM) Center.

5. Science Communications

5.1 2014 Activities

In the past year we wrote and distributed eight news releases highlighting published results from NESCent-sponsored projects, on topics ranging from how barnyard chickens came to be, to why some species have superior smarts, to how plants evolved to cope with cold.

Reporters receive these releases through “Eurekaalert,” a news service sponsored by AAAS that nearly 10,000 registered reporters look to for forthcoming science news and story ideas. NESCent news releases for the 2013-2014 reporting year received more than 30,000 page views on the Eurekaalert website alone, not to mention the numbers of viewers that followed in newspaper and magazine articles, blogs and other mainstream media outlets. In 2013-2014, NESCent-sponsored research was featured in more than 60 articles in the mainstream media — in outlets such as *Science News*, *National Geographic*, *Science Magazine* and *Discover*. The media outlets that covered our science collectively reach millions of readers each month, a readership that no academic journal could achieve.

What follows is a list of our news releases from the past year, and the media coverage that followed for each one. For a full list of media coverage in 2013-2014 please see the Appendix:

[Wild connection: What animal mating and courtship tell us about human relationships.](#) June 25, 2014. Sex-crazed turtles, confused bees, and cheating swans. These are just a few of the things animal behavior expert and NESCent postdoc Jennifer Verdolin discusses in this new book that blends humor and science to show the similarities between humans and animals when it comes to dating and relationships. Picked up by [WUNC](#), [The Scientist](#), [Wired](#), [Slate Magazine](#) and the [Toronto Star](#).

[In the age of open science, repurposing and reproducing research pose their own challenges.](#) May 12, 2014. Growing numbers of researchers are making the data underlying their publications freely available online, largely in response to data sharing policies at journals and funding agencies. But in the age of open science, improving access is one thing, repurposing and reproducing research is another. A team of NESCent researchers experienced this firsthand when they tried to answer a seemingly simple question: what percentage of plants in the world are woody?

[Animals with bigger brains, broader diets have better self control.](#) April 24, 2014. The largest study of animal intelligence to-date finds that animals with bigger brains and broader diets have better self-control. The results are part of a long history of research aimed at understanding why some species are able to do things like make and use tools, read social cues, or even understand basic math, and others aren't. By convincing animal experts across the globe to conduct the same set of experiments, NESCent researchers are testing ideas about how cognitive differences in the animal kingdom came to be in a more rigorous way than has been possible before. Picked up by [The New York Times](#) and the [National Science Foundation](#).

[Plants with dormant seeds give rise to more species.](#) *April 18, 2014.* Seeds that sprout as soon as they're planted may be good news for a garden. But wild plants need to be more careful. In the wild, a plant whose seeds sprouted at the first warm spell or rainy day would risk disaster. More than just an insurance policy against late frosts or unexpected dry spells, it turns out that seed dormancy has long-term advantages too: Plants whose seeds put off sprouting until conditions are more certain give rise to more species, finds a new study by NESCent researcher Rafael Rubio de Casas.

[Ancient DNA offers clues to how barnyard chickens came to be.](#) *April 21, 2014.* Ancient DNA adds a twist to the story of how barnyard chickens came to be, finds a study by the NESCent working group, "Domestication as an Evolutionary Phenomenon." Analyzing DNA from the bones of chickens that lived 200-2300 years ago in Europe, the researchers report that some of the traits we associate with modern domestic chickens — such as their yellowish skin — only became widespread in the last 500 years, much more recently than previously thought. Picked up by [Ars Technica](#), [Nature](#) and [Public Radio International](#).

[Study offers clues to how plants evolved to cope with cold.](#) *December 22, 2013.* NESCent researchers have found new clues to how plants evolved to withstand wintry weather. In a study in the journal *Nature*, the team constructed an evolutionary tree of more than 32,000 species of flowering plants — the largest time-scaled evolutionary tree to date. By combining their tree with freezing exposure records and leaf and stem data for thousands of species, the researchers were able to reconstruct how plants evolved to cope with cold as they spread across the globe. The results suggest that many plants acquired characteristics that helped them thrive in colder climates — such as dying back to the roots in winter — long before they first encountered freezing. Picked up by [Futurity](#).

[Biodiversity higher in the tropics, but species more likely to arise at higher latitudes.](#) *November 2013.* A study of 2300 species of mammals and 6700 species of birds offers a counterintuitive explanation for why there are more species in the tropics than at higher latitudes. Researchers found that while the tropics harbor more species, the number of subspecies increases in the harsher environments typical of higher latitudes. The results suggest that the latitudinal diversity gradient may be due higher species turnover — speciation counterbalanced by extinction — towards the poles than near the equator. Featuring work by NESCent working group members Carlos Botero and Rebecca Safran.

To support coverage of evolution and related fields beyond the center, we have two programs:

NESCent sponsors a [blog contest](#) and conference travel fellowship for evolutionary bloggers. To apply for the award, writers are required to submit a blog post that highlights current or emerging evolutionary research. Winners receive \$750 apiece to cover travel and lodging expenses to attend [ScienceOnline](#), a science communication conference held each winter in North Carolina. Our final call for entries to our evolution blog contest went out in September 2014, with winners announced in December 2014. Our 2014 winners were New York-based freelancers Elizabeth Preston and Nidhi Subbaraman.

NESCent's [journalist-in-residence](#) program, now in its fourth and final year, offers a unique opportunity for reporters, producers, and editors to work on an ambitious, exciting project of their own choosing with an evolutionary focus. Journalists of all nationalities are welcome to apply. The final calls for

proposals to our journalist-in-residence program went out on January 15, 2014. In our final year we welcomed the following writers:

- An entomologist, freelance writer and photographer at the National Museum of Natural History, Mark Moffett joined us for three months in the fall of 2014 to work on a book project titled, “Human Identity and the Evolution of Societies.”
- A staff writer for a daily newspaper in Montana called the Missoulian, Rob Chaney spent two weeks at NESCent in the spring of 2014 researching the extent of the evolutionary changes we may see in the Rocky Mountain region as climate change and human encroachment progress. His research was part of a year-long project to mark the 50th anniversary of the Wilderness Act.
- A science journalist and multimedia producer based in Pakistan, Suhail Yusuf joined us for three months in the summer of 2014 to work on an ongoing book project about fossil discoveries in Pakistan, to be translated into regional languages of Pakistan.

5.2 2015 Plans

We are creating a special bumper issue of the quarterly newsletter in time for the NESCent Celebration in November. In addition to the typical contents comprised of longer features and news updates, we will also revisit a selection of past stories. The double-length issue will include brief summaries of the accomplishments from the last ten years for each of the branches of the center (Science, Education & Outreach, Informatics, etc.). The director’s letter and an article on the continuation of NESCent research in the form of a new Evolutionary Medicine synthesis center (Tri-CEM) will serve as bookends to the center’s legacy. We will leave the possibility open for issuing additional newsletters in 2015 should we have compelling news to share with our readership.

Robin Smith left NESCent in August to work as a science writer at Duke News. Nicole Duncan has assumed some of her responsibilities including creating the newsletter; managing NESCent’s social media presence; updating the website; and writing press releases. She will continue these activities into 2015.

NESCent will put out another call for proposals for a Journalist-in-Residence with a deadline of December 1, 2014. The recipient expected to arrive in January or early February 2015. Due to the ongoing contraction of the NESCent community, the Education & Outreach department will collaborate with Communications to ensure the visiting journalist has a viable network in NESCent or the greater Triangle.

6. Assessment

NESCent's mission is to "promote the synthesis of information, concepts and knowledge to address significant, emerging, or novel questions in evolutionary science and its applications. NESCent achieves this by supporting research and education across disciplinary, institutional, geographic, and demographic boundaries." NESCent's assessment program seeks to evaluate how successfully we are fulfilling this mission. Specifically, we apply a three-tiered evaluation system focused on people, products, and process.

1. People: Does NESCent support research and education across disciplinary, institutional, geographic, and demographic boundaries?
2. Products: Are NESCent scientists addressing questions that are significant, emerging, and/or novel in evolutionary science?
3. Process: Does NESCent accomplish (2) by promoting the synthesis of information, concepts and knowledge both within and beyond direct Center activities?

6.1 2014 Activities

6.1.1 Ongoing Activities

For Tier 2 assessment in year 10, we continued to focus on building accurate records of publications and grants resulting from NESCent activities. By establishing this record, we were able to easily produce up-to-date estimates of the number of publications and citations for the annual report and the assessment report earlier this year. We also take advantage of ImpactStory.org, itself incubated through a Sloan grant to NESCent, to measure the usage of NESCent publications and other products (such as datasets and software) by both researchers and the public. ImpactStory allows us to capture measures including the number of bookmarks by Mendeley users, mentions in Wikipedia or on leading blogs, downloads of data in Dryad, and forks of software repositories on Github, and to systematically compare these measures to those of non-NESCent products.

Our assessment team continues to actively collaborating with an assessment working group (Advancing Theory and Research on Scientific Synthesis) jointly supported by NCEAS and NESCent. The third working group meeting of this group will occur in December at NESCent. NESCent has previously supported one other meeting of this group. The group brings together scientists who lead and conduct synthetic research with a diverse group of experts on scientific collaboration and research evaluation. The aim is to advance our understanding of synthesis and develop new empirical approaches for investigating it longitudinally and comparatively. One objective of the group is to map synthesis outcomes in relation to broader scientific and disciplinary areas, based on the collection of abstracts from all articles from all journals published by NCEAS and NESCent from 1991-present.

As part of a broader assessment program within NESCent, the 'Science of Science Project' began in 2009 with the goal of studying how participants engage in interdisciplinary collaborations that are both

collocated and distributed. NESCent offered a unique opportunity to examine how researchers from different universities and different departments would work together in person (during meetings at NESCent) as well as at a distance (in between meetings while at their home institutions).

Under the direction of Jonathon Cummings (Associate Professor of Management, Fuqua School of Business, Duke University), survey data has been collected from a total of roughly 50 working groups and 20 catalysis meetings over the past 5 years. In the first few years, two hackathons and four post-docs were also included in the study, though the focus shifted to working groups and catalysis meetings given the larger sample size needed for statistical analysis.

Below is an overview of the data collected from 2009-2014.

Project	2009-2014		Meeting	WG Surveyed 2009-2013	WG Surveyed 2014 (so far)	WG Scheduled 2014 (so far)
	# Groups	# Participants				
Hackathons	2	55 (135 Surveys)	1 st WG	32	2	
Post-Doc Interviews	-	4	2 nd WG	27	3	1
Catalysis Meetings	19	337	3 rd WG	30	1	2
Working Groups (WG)	51 (112 surveys)	791 (1449 surveys)	4 th WG	14	3	3
TOTAL	70	1187	Total WG	103		
			CM	19		

Prior analyses of the working group survey data have shown interesting patterns in terms of why participants decided to join the working groups and how participants perceive their working group collaborations relative to their non-NESCent collaborations. In particular, at the 1st working group meeting, participants report “To foster future research collaborations” and “To meet and network with people in your field” as the two most important reasons for joining. Furthermore, they report “Scientific questions addressed”, “Research methods used,” and “Disciplinary topics involved” as the three ways they expect their working groups to be most different from their other collaborations. It is important to note that a majority of working group members had not collaborated with one another prior to the working group, and less than one-third had participated in a NESCent activity prior to the working group.

At the 2nd working group meeting, participants report working with (on average) a small subset of the team while they were at their home institutions. Put differently, participants tended to work with a few others on their working groups in between meetings, suggesting division of labor and/or working alone on their piece of the project. For those who did work together, participants primarily used email and phone/skype, as well as meeting in person at academic conferences. On the second working group survey, participants reported being most satisfied with “The quality of participant ideas and discussion”, “The diversity of disciplinary expertise of participants,” and “The diversity of career levels among participants.”

At the 3rd working group meeting, participants reported almost identical levels of working together with (few) others in between meetings, they used the same methods of communication, and they were satisfied with the same aspects of the working group. The primary difference in the third working group survey, as expected, was that participants starting having products to report (e.g., publications, presentations, software).

Given the current sample size for the 4th meeting (survey data from ~14 working groups vs ~30 for the first three meetings), analyses are speculative. The number of reported products is greater for the fourth meeting relative to the earlier meetings, though participants continue to report only working with a small subset of other members in between meetings. And in the fourth and final survey, participants are still likely to report that “Scientific questions addressed”, “Research methods used,” and “Disciplinary topics involved” distinguish their NESCent working group from non-NESCent collaborations. However, they also report that “Competitive grants applied for,” “Academic conferences attended,” and “Journals targeted for publication” are actually more like their other collaborations than they originally expected (i.e., compared with their survey responses from the first working group meeting).

Additional analyses incorporating the most recent 2014 data will be ready for the NESCent celebration on November 22-23, 2014.

6.1.2 Assessment Highlights

- Table 1 summarizes the products and outputs of NESCent’s activities. NESCent’s h-index continues to rise. In 2010 our h-index was 27, 32 in 2011, 43 in 2012, and 57 in 2013. As of this report our current h-index is 69. Our papers have accumulated 19,479 citations compared to the 13,219 citations from last year at this time. The average citation count per paper is 30.92, up from 23.9 last year (Figure 1).
- 16.2% of NESCent publications occur in five leading multidisciplinary science journals (*Nature*, *Science*, *Trends in Ecology and Evolution*, *Proceedings of the Royal Society B*, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, US*).
- The average number of coauthors per paper has continued to stay steady at a little less than four from 2009-2013. This year we have seen an increase to ~5 (Figure 2).
- NESCent continues to see an influx of new visitors into the center (Figure 3). The linear and steadily increasing trend, with no sign of an asymptote, suggests we continued to draw new communities into NESCent. We also continue to maintain a 50:50 ratio of emerging to experienced scientists in NESCent activities (Figure 4).
- In total, papers published as a result of NESCent activities have been written about blogs 149, on Facebook 90, on Google+ 36, Tweeted 1997, and on Wikipedia 118 times. Readers on Mendeley have accessed NESCent papers 47,630 times. In terms of data associated with NESCent papers, data packages have been viewed 835 and downloaded 210 times at Dryad.

6.2 Final Plans

In year ten with news that NESCent will not continue, we have been concentrating our efforts on outlining a final assessment report to summarize the productivity and impact of the center. Final analyses will also be summarized into a peer-reviewed publication for an open access journal by the end of the year. Our collaboration with the Working Group on Advancing Theory and Research on Scientific Synthesis, and our Science of Science project, will allow us to assess a rich range of factors that

contribute to successful projects and the impact of our activities on the participants, including the extent to which participation increases the likelihood of successful grant funding. We intend to publish our results and contribute to the relatively thin literature on the sociology and policy of synthetic science.

Table 1: NESCent by the numbers

Number of	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	Total
Participants	8	169	517	952	589	796	690	1100	744	878	625	7068
Software/ Datesets			1	21	25	16	8	14	34	19	1	139
Publications	1	2	26	44	46	71	98	109	121	64	49	631
News Coverage				4	5	45	43	65	100	25	64	351
Catalysis Meetings			4	6	3	4	5	5	7	0	12	46
Active Working Groups		2	9	15	17	20	22	21	15	12	20	153
New Postdoctoral Fellows		5	7	4	3	8	4	6	4	4	0	46
Active Sabbatical Scholars		4	5	1	5	3	5	5	5	5	9	47
Courses				5	11	6	7	4	6	4	3	46
Course Participants				75	84	142	57	123	169	97	81	828

Figure 1: Cumulative number of citations per year based on all NESCent publications

Average number of authors per paper

Figure 2: Average number of coauthors per paper per year on NESCent related publications

Figure 3: Cumulative new visitors per month

Figure 4: Percentage of professional stages participating in NESCent activities per year

7. Administration

The primary focus of the past year's activities within the administration at NESCent has been to increase the visibility of working group, sabbatical scholar and short-term visitor support as we meet the demands of the final years of NESCent. The administrative staff was involved in organizing the Evolution 2014 meeting, both during the lead-up to the conference, and at the conference itself. In particular, Danielle Wilson-Wiggins and Stephanie Risbon lead the operational effort for Evolution 2014, ably assisted by other staff at NESCent. The team has continued to increase efficiency, by building better tools and processes as well increasing staff training opportunities. In addition, staff is focused on developing a detailed timeline for the wind-down and closure of the NSF award November 30, 2015.

7.1 2014 Activities

As NESCent winds down, we expect that staff will leave to take up other opportunities. Transitions in 2014 included Robin Smith, NESCent's communications manager, who has moved to the Duke Office of News and Communication as a Science Writer, Mercedes Gosby, IT Analyst, and David Palmer, IT Analyst, who moved to the Duke University Office of Information Technology. Hilmar Lapp, Assistant Director of Informatics, is undertaking a gradual phase out of responsibility to the Genome Computational Biology Center in Duke Medicine, with 60% of his time as of October 1, 2014. Hilmar will continue a fractional appointment at the Center until June 2015. On the Logistics team, we said goodbye to Jeff Sturkey who supported the Education, Outreach and Communications group and NESCent Academy. He has moved to the Special Events Office of University Development at Duke. Postdoctoral Scholars Dan Ksepka (Bruce Museum), Kate Hertweck (University of Texas, Tyler), Adam Smith (Field Museum), Jonathan Lombard (University of Exeter) and Jeremy Van Cleve (University of Kentucky) will all leave (or have already left) NESCent for professional opportunities by December 2014. We are delighted that so many staff and postdocs have been successful in moving to other opportunities, but sad that we will no longer benefit from their presence and exuberance. We place on record our sincere and deeply-felt gratitude for their service.

We also welcomed Nicole Duncan who joined NESCent in June 2013, and whose experience in journalism and communication as well as her willing approach to undertake new projects and support existing ones has been an important part of the success of NESCent during 2013-14.

7.2 Transitions for 2015

We continue to support the career transition of our team through a focused professional career transition program intended to support and facilitate healthy career progression for staff. Consequently, we continue to offer staff the opportunity to attend courses, workshops and training. Both Barbara Mitchell and Lori Houjak will work toward their Advanced Grant Management certification in 2014-15, while Danielle and Stephanie continue certification process for Special Events.

We anticipate ongoing working group meetings (32) through June 2015, hosting a final symposium at the Washington Duke Inn in November 2014, welcoming 5 graduate students for fellowships in Fall

2014, hosting a Triangle Scholar and several sabbatical scholars throughout the year, and 13 short-term visitors. While maintaining this schedule, the team will also focus on archiving all print and electronic records of the 10-year Center, managing the reduction in force issues for a staff of 20 most of whom will end their time at NESCent in June 2015, closing the physical Center in July, 2015, providing final reporting in September 2015, and closing the financial grant record in November 2015.

8. External Funding

Title	PI	Funding Agency	Dates	Direct	Indirect	Total
Funded						
<i>NESCent - Duke</i>						
PIRE: Understanding Marine Biodiversity Along Geographical and Anthropogenic Stress Gradients	Allen Rodrigo (Forrest Rohwer)	NSF (Subaward from San Diego State University)	1/1/2013 - 12/31/2017	\$65,054	\$18,566	\$83,620
Collaborative Research: Automated and Community-Driven Synthesis of the Tree of Life	Karen Cranston	NSF	6/1/2012 - 5/31/2015	\$723,338	\$176,656	\$899,994
Materials and Workshops for Cyberinfrastructure Education in Biology	Hilmar Lapp	NSF (subaward from MSU BEACON)	8/1/2013 – 7/31/2015	\$70,446	\$3,907	\$74,353
EAGER: NESCent Ambassador Program	Allen Rodrigo & Jory Wientraub	NSF	5/1/2011 - 4/30/2014	\$239,276	\$25,239	\$264,515

Meeting: The Shape of the Future: A Workshop to Consolidate and Advance the Field of Evolutionary Developmental Biology	Allen Rodrigo & Cassandra Extavour	NSF	8/1/2012 - 7/31/2014	\$87,503	\$12,495	\$99,998
ABI Innovation: A Novel Database and Ontology for Evolutionary Analysis of Mammalian Feeding Physiology	Hilmar Lapp (Chris Wall)	NSF (Subaward from Duke's Dept. of Evolutionary Anthropology)	7/1/2011 - 6/30/2014	\$27,490	\$15,670	\$43,160
ABI Development: Dryad: Scalable and Sustainable Infrastructure for the Publication of Data	Todd Vision	NSF	3/1/2012 - 2/29/2016	\$2,027,103	\$376,533	\$2,403,636
DataONE: Observation Network for Earth	Todd Vision (William Michener)	NSF (Subaward from Univ of New Mexico)	8/1/2009- 10/31/2014	\$183,897	\$52,410	\$236,307
Open Tree of Life Invited submission	Karen Cranston	NSF	6/1/2015 – 5/31/2017	\$837,648	\$218,984	\$1,056,632
Evolutionary Biology of the Built Environment	Craig McClain	Sloan Foundation	12/01/2012- 12/01/2014	\$57,714	\$8,657	\$66,371

Using the New Digital Libraries to Make Discoveries about Biodiversity & Evolution	Craig McClain	Lounsbery Foundation	8/01/2013-7/31/2015	\$43,478	\$6,522	\$50,000
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Total Duke Funded **\$4,362,947** **\$915,639** **\$5,278,586**

NESCent - UNC

ABI Development: Ontology-Enabled Reasoning Across Phenotypes from Evolution and Model Organisms	Todd Vision (Paula Mabee)	NSF (Subaward from Univ of South Dakota)	7/1/2011-6/30/2015	\$1,127,219	\$178,572	\$1,305,791
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Total UNC Funded **\$1,127,219** **\$178,572** **\$1,305,791**

NESCent - NCSU

ABI Development: Dryad: Scalable and Sustainable Infrastructure for the Publication of Data	Kristin Antelman (Todd Vision)	NSF (Subaward from Duke Univ)	3/1/2012 - 2/29/2016	Included under Duke University's prime award	\$18,827
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Total NCSU Funded **\$18,827**

Pending

NESCent - Duke

Dimensions: Diversification and Size in Metazoans	Craig McClain	NSF	1/1/2013 - 12/31/2015	\$452,195	\$122,089	\$574,284
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Total Duke Pending				\$452,195	\$122,089	\$574,284
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NESCent - UNC

None Currently Pending						
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Total UNC Pending				-	-	-
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NESCent - NCSU

None Currently Pending						
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Total NCSU Pending				-	-	-
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Total Funded						\$6,603,204
Total Pending						\$ 574,284
Total Funded and Pending						\$7,177,488

List of Appendices

- A. Disciplines of Supported Projects in Year 9
- B. Demographics of PI's and Co-PI's in Year 9
 - 1. Gender
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Appendix A: Disciplines of Supported Projects in Year 10

	Meeting		Visiting Scholar					Total
	Catalysis Meeting	Course		Graduate Fellow	Journalist in Residence	Long-term Sabbatical	Short-term Visitor	
Applied Evolution	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	2
Behavior or Neurobiology	1	0	0	3	1	0	3	8
Biodiversity	1	0	0	1	1	0	6	9
Comparative Biology	1	1	0	0	0	1	3	6
Development	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2
Education	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	3
Evolutionary Ecology or Population Biology	2	0	1	2	1	0	11	17
Genomics or Proteomics	3	0	0	0	0	0	1	4
Molecular Evolution	1	1	0	0	0	0	3	5
Paleontology	1	1	0	1	2	0	0	5
Phylogeography or Speciation	0	1	0	2	0	0	1	4
Physiology or Functional Morphology	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	3
Population or Evolutionary Genetics	0	0	0	2	1	0	1	4
Systematics or Phylogenetics	1	2	0	3	0	0	3	9
Other	1	0	0	1	0	2	7	11
Climate Change	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	2
Evolutionary Medicine	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Human Evolution	0	0	1	2	1	1	0	5
Origins of Life	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Synthetic Biology	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1

Appendix B1: Gender of Project PI's and Co-PI's in Year 10

	Catalysis Meeting	Graduate Fellow	Journalist in Residence	Long-term Sabbatical	Postdoctoral Fellow	Short-term Visitor	Working Group	Total
Female	10	8	0	2	4	23	17	64
Male	18	9	2	5	5	16	21	76
Total	28	17	2	7	9	39	38	140

Appendix B2: Ethnicity of Project PI's and Co-PI's in Year 10

	Catalysis Meeting	Graduate Fellow	Journalist in Residence	Long-term Sabbatical	Postdoctoral Fellow	Short-term Visitor	Working Group	Total
Hispanic or Latino	0	1	0	0	1	0	3	5
Not Hispanic or Latino	24	15	2	7	6	35	34	123
Do not wish to provide	4	1	0	0	2	4	1	12
Total	28	17	2	7	9	39	38	140

Appendix B3: Race of Project PI's and Co-PI's in Year 10

	Catalysis Meeting	Graduate Fellow	Journalist in Residence	Long-term Sabbatical	Postdoctoral Fellow	Short-term Visitor	Working Group	Total
Asian	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	6
Black or African	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	2
Hispanic or Latino	0	0	0	0	1	0	3	4
White	22	14	1	6	6	33	33	115
Do not wish to provide	5	1	0	0	2	4	1	13
Total	28	17	2	7	9	39	38	140

Appendix B4: Nationality of Project PI's and Co-PI's in Year 10

	Catalysis Meeting	Graduate Fellow	Journalist in Residence	Long-term Sabbatical	Postdoctoral Fellow	Short-term Visitor	Working Group	Total
US Citizen	22	14	1	4	7	31	24	103
Permanent Resident	0	0	0	1	0	1	3	5
Non-US Citizen	5	2	1	2	2	6	11	29
Do not wish to provide	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	3
Total	28	17	2	7	9	39	38	140

Appendix C1: Gender of Participants in Year 10

	Catalysis Meeting	Course	Working Group	Total
Female	81	30	188	299
Male	132	35	234	401
Do not wish to provide	0	0	1	1
No Answer	14	5	19	38
Total	227	70	442	739

Appendix C2: Ethnicity of Participants in Year 10

	Catalysis Meeting	Course	Working Group	Total
Hispanic or Latino	42	18	59	119
Not Hispanic or Latino	147	42	322	511
Do not wish to provide	22	5	42	69
No Answer	16	5	19	40
Total	227	70	442	739

Appendix C3: Race of Participants in Year 10

	Catalysis Meeting	Course	Working Group	Total
	14	6	19	39
American Indian or Alaska Native	0	0	3	3
Asian	20	4	28	52
Black or African American	16	4	26	46
Do not wish to provide	21	6	49	76
Hispanic or Latino	22	11	30	63
Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific	2	4	6	12
White	132	35	281	448
Total	227	70	442	739

Appendix C4: Nationality of Participants in Year 10

	Catalysis Meeting	Course	Working Group	Total
US Citizen	115	27	225	367
Permanent Resident	19	8	54	81
Non-US Citizen	79	30	144	253
No Answer	14	5	19	38
Total	227	70	442	739

Appendix D: Countries of Unique Participants' Institution as Self-reported

Participants by Country

	Total
ARGENTINA	2
AUSTRALIA	25
BELGIUM	2
BRAZIL	9
CANADA	30
DENMARK	1
FINLAND	2
FRANCE	10
GERMANY	9
GREECE	2
HUNGARY	1
INDIA	1
INDONESIA	1
IRELAND	1
ISRAEL	4
ITALY	1
MEXICO	2
NETHERLANDS	6
NEW ZEALAND	7
No Answer	45
POLAND	1
PORTUGAL	1
SAUDI ARABIA	1
SOUTH AFRICA	6
SPAIN	6
SWEDEN	11
SWITZERLAND	11
THAILAND	1
THE NETHERLANDS	1
UNITED KINGDOM	48
United States	490
Total	738

Appendix E: U.S. States of Unique Participants' Institution as Self-reported

Participants by State

Appendix E: U.S. States of Participant Institutions

	Total
AL	4
AZ	12
CA	49
CO	24
CT	13
DC	17
DE	1
FL	16
GA	9
HI	5
IA	4
ID	6
IL	19
IN	12
KS	4
KY	3
LA	4
MA	42
MD	8
MI	15
MN	6
MO	3
MS	5
MT	2
NC	49
NE	3
NH	1
NJ	5
NM	7
NY	33
OH	26
OK	2
OR	2
PA	19
RI	1
SC	1
TN	7
TX	22

	Total
UT	5
VA	8
WA	13
WI	5
WY	1
Total	490

Appendix F: Detailed List of Activities and Participants in Year 10

Catalysis Meeting

The co-evolution of plants and fire and consequences for the Earth system

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=423

Dates: 2/18/2014 - 2/21/2014

PI

Sally Archibald

Institution

Council for Scientific and Industrial Research

CoPI

Caroline Lehmann

University of Edinburgh

Participants

Byron Lamont	Curtin University
Caroline Lehmann	University of Edinburgh
Owen F Price	University of Wollongong
Colin P Osborne	University of Sheffield
Glenn Moncrieff	Frankfurt University
Tianhua He	Curtin University
Brendan Rogers	University of California, Irvine
Steve Higgins	University of Otago
Guido van der Werf	VU University Amsterdam
Amy Zanne	George Washington University
Kyle Dexter	University of Edinburgh
Sally Archibald	University of the Witwatersrand
Juli Pausas	Spanish National Research Council
Bill Hoffman	North Carolina State University
Claire Belcher	University of Exeter
Beth Forrestel	Yale University
Ross Bradstock	University of Wollongong
Brad Ripley	Rhodes University
Dylan Schwilk	Texas Tech University
Marcelo Simon	Embrapa - Brazilian Agricultural Research Corporat
William Bond	University of Cape Town
Caroline A E Stromberg	University of Washington
Anne-Laure Daniau	CNRS
Merritt Turetsky	University of Guelph
Michelle Greve	University of Pretoria
Daniel McGlenn	Utah State University

Anthropogenic Sensory Stimuli as Drivers of Evolution: A conceptual synthesis and roadmap for an integrated citizen-science research network

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=422

Dates: 4/24/2014 - 4/28/2014

PI

Caren Cooper

Institution

Cornell Lab of Ornithology

CoPI

Clinton D Francis

Jesse Barber

NESCent

Boise State University

Participants

Davide Dominoni	University of Glasgow
Caren Cooper	Cornell Lab of Ornithology
Jesse Barber	Boise State University
Chris McClure	Peregrine Fund
Clinton D Francis	California Polytechnic State University
Paul Allen	Cornell Lab of Ornithology
Kamiel Spoelstra	Netherlands Institute of Ecology
Constance Walker	GLOBE at Night
Graeme Shannon	Colorado State University
Sarah Goodwin	University of Massachusetts
Kurt Fristrup	National Park Service
Chris Kyba	Leibniz-Institute of Freshwater Ecology and Inland
Rich Stedman	Cornell University
Akito Kawahara	University of Florida
Holly Menninger	North Carolina State University
Ariel Levi Simons	Natural History Museum of Los Angeles County
Andrea Wiggins	Cornell Lab of Ornithology
Bora Zivkovic	.None
Margaret Voss	Syracuse University
Derrick Taff	Pennsylvania State University
John Swaddle	College of William and Mary
Travis Longcore	University of Southern California
Muki Haklay	University College London
David Luther	George Mason University
Dan Mennitt	National Park Service (Fort Collins,co)
Rob Dunn	North Carolina State University
Elizabeth Derryberry	Tulane University
Jenn Newton	The Pennsylvania State University
Erik Aschehoug	North Carolina State University
Steven Gray	University of Massachusetts

A Deeper Look into the Avian Brain: Using Modern Imaging to Unlock Ancient Endocasts

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=436

Dates: 5/12/2014 - 5/15/2014

<u>PI</u>	<u>Institution</u>
Amy Balanoff	Stony Brook University (Stony Brook, NY)

<u>CoPI</u>	<u>Institution</u>
N. Adam Smith	NESCent
Daniel Ksepka	NESCent

Participants

Christopher Torres	University of North Carolina-Wilmington
Lawrence Witmer	Ohio University
Julia Clarke	University of Texas-Austin
Bhart-Anjan Bhullar	Yale University
Eugenia Gold	American Museum of Natural History
Mark Norell	American Museum of Natural History
Catherine Early	Ohio University
Ashley Morhardt	Ohio University
Ryan Ridgely	Ohio University Heritage College of Osteopathic Me
Alexandra Wright	University of California - San Diego
Gabriel Bever	New York Institute of Technology
Jeroen Smaers	Stony Brook University
Jeremy Corfield	University of Alberta
Claudia Tambussi	CICTERRA (CONICET-UNC)
Daniel Field	Yale University
Paul Vaska	Stony Brook University
Marcel van Tuinen	University of North Carolina-Wilmington
Amy Balanoff	Stony Brook University (Stony Brook, NY)
Matt Colbert	University of Texas-Austin
Richard Paul Scofield	Canterbury Museum
Federico Degrange	CICTERRA (CONICET-UNC)
Daniel Ksepka	NESCent
N. Adam Smith	NESCent
Harry Jerison	University of California-Los Angeles
Aki Watanabe	American Museum of Natural History
Stig Walsh	National Museums Scotland
Erich Jarvis	Duke University
Paul Gignac	Oklahoma State University Center for Health Scienc
Louis Lefebvre	McGill University
Harvey Karten	University of California-San Diego
Jesus Marugon-Lobon	Universidad Autonoma de Madrid
Lindsay Zanno	North Carolina Museum of Natural Sciences

Integrating Organismal and Applied Perspectives on Animal Venom Diversity

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=420

Dates: 9/22/2014 - 9/24/2014

PI

Marymegan Daly

Institution

Ohio State University

CoPI

H. Lisle Gibbs

Ohio State University

Participants

Darin Rokyta	Florida State University
Juliette Gorson	Hunter College
Juan Calvete	Instituto Biomedicina Valencia
Ana Moura-da-Silva	Instituto Butantan
William Smith	University of Kansas
Yehu Moran	Hebrew University of Jerusalem
Ashlee Rowe	Michigan State University
Mark Margres	Florida State University
Nicholas Casewell	Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine
Matt Holding	Ohio State University
Kartik Sunagar	The Hebrew University of Jerusalem
Inacio Junqueira de Azevedo	Instituto Butantan
Ronald Jenner	Natural History Museum
Sharon Jansa	University of Minnesota
Mary Oconnell	Dublin City University
Eivind Undheim	University of Queensland
Steve Mackessy	University of Northern Colorado
Ricardo Rodriguez de la Vega	University Paris-Sud
Mande Holford	Hunter College, CUNY/AMNH
Marymegan Daly	Ohio State University
Jason Macrander	Ohio State University
Ray Norton	Monash University
H. Lisle Gibbs	Ohio State University
Felipe Graziotin	University of Sao Paulo
Bryan Fry	University of Queensland
Tom Duda	University of Michigan

Evolution and community ecology of host-associated microbiota

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=437

Dates: 10/6/2014 - 10/8/2014

<u>PI</u>	<u>Institution</u>
Elena Litchman	Michigan State University (East Lansing, MI)
<u>CoPI</u>	
Thomas Schmidt	University of Michigan-Ann Arbor
<u>Participants</u>	
Elena Litchman	Michigan State University (East Lansing, MI)
Thomas Schmidt	University of Michigan-Ann Arbor

Scaling evolution from genomes to ecosystems in peatmosses (Sphagnum)

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=441

Dates: 10/13/2014 - 10/15/2014

<u>PI</u>	<u>Institution</u>
Jon Shaw	Duke University
<u>CoPI</u>	
David Weston	Oak Ridge National Laboratory
Merritt Turetsky	University of Guelph
<u>Participants</u>	
Jon Shaw	Duke University
Merritt Turetsky	University of Guelph
David Weston	Oak Ridge National Laboratory

Developing Best Practices for Teaching Evolution in the Social Sciences

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=442

Dates: 10/16/2014 - 10/19/2014

<u>PI</u>	<u>Institution</u>
Cristine Legare	The University of Texas at Austin (Austin, TX)

CoPI

John Opfer
Andrew Shtulman

Ohio State University
Occidental College

Participants

Cristine Legare

The University of Texas at Austin (Austin, TX)

BeeBiome:Omic approaches for understanding bee-microbe relationships

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=421

Dates: 10/20/2014 - 10/24/2014

PI

Benjamin Dainat

Institution

Swiss Bee Research Centre - Agroscope

CoPI

Philipp Engel
Joachim De Miranda
lantbruksuniversitet
Jay D. Evans

Yale University
Honeybee Research Group Sveriges
Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
USDA Bee laboratory, Beltsville, MD

Participants

Benjamin Dainat

Swiss Bee Research Centre - Agroscope

New resources for ancient organisms – enabling dragonfly genomics

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=465

Dates: 11/3/2014 - 11/7/2014

PI

Seth Bybee

Institution

Brigham Young University

CoPI

Phill Watts
Maren Wellenreuther

University of Liverpool
Lund University

Participants

Janne Sweagers
Anton Surorov
Seth Bybee
Haley Wightman
Ruud Schilder
Maren Wellenreuther
Phill Watts
Alex Cordoba
Bengt Hansson
Erik Svensson
Jessica Ware
Olalla Lorenzo-Carball
Rosa Sanchez-Guillen
Ryo Futahashi
Yuma Takahashi
Pallavi Chauhan
Robby Stoks

University of Leuven
Bringham Young University
Bringham Young University
Bringham Young University
Penn State University
Lund University
Liverpool (Oulu)
UNAM
Lund University
Lund University
Rutgers University
Vigo University
Lund University
AIST
Tohoku University
Lund University
University of Leuven

SimBank: Planning population genetic simulations to test statistical genetics software

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=419

Dates: 11/10/2014 - 11/12/2014

PI

Michael Whitlock

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Matthew Hahn
Victoria Sork

Indiana University
UCLA

Participants

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Victoria Sork
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University of British Columbia
UCLA
Indiana University

Realising the full potential of long-term evolution experiments [OBJ]

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=466

Dates: 11/18/2014 - 11/21/2014

PI

Robert Lanfear

Institution

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CoPI

Richard Lenski
Hanna Kokko

Michigan State University
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Participants

Robert Lanfear

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Course

Generation and Analysis of High-Throughput Sequencing Data for Phylogenetics and Phylogeography

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=380

Dates: 7/14/2014 - 7/20/2014

PI

Emily Lemmon

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CoPI

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Vinson Doyle	Louisiana State University
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Alison Nazareno	Universidade de S•o Paulo
Jacob Berv	Cornell University
James Starrett	San Diego State University
DIANA PAZMINO	James Cook University
Renan Bosque	University of Mississippi
Charles Davis	Harvard University
Alejandro Zuluaga	University of Wisconsin-Madison
Stuart Nielsen	University of Mississippi
Sarah Lemer	Harvard University
Emily Ellis	University of Santa Barbara
Julissa Roncal	Memorial University of Newfoundland
Elisandra Chiquito	Universidade de Sao Paulo
Nisa Karimi	University of Wisconsin - Madison
Carolina Granados Mendoza	Universidad Nacional Autonoma de Mexico-UNAM
Jennifer Zaspel	Purdue University
Ning Zhang	Smithsonian Institution
Cecile Ane	University of Wisconsin-Madison
Yi-Hsin Erica Tsai	University of Colorado Boulder
Paul Frandsen	Rutgers University
Ryan Kepler	USDA-ARS
Adela Roa-Varon	Virginia Institute of Marine Science (VIMS), Willi
Liming Cai	Harvard University
Paul Hime	University of Kentucky
Christian Rabeling	University of Rochester
Emily Lemmon	Florida State University (Tallahassee,FL)
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Jeremy Brown	Louisiana State University
Colin Favret	University of Montreal
Frank Burbrink	College of Staten Island/CUNY
Katherine Brooks	Columbia University
Alan Lemmon	Florida State University
Dave Weisrock	University of Kentucky
Seth Bybee	Brigham Young University

Paleobiological and Phylogenetic Approaches to Macroevolution

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=430

Dates: 7/22/2014 - 7/29/2014

PI

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Keck Science Department, Claremont McKenna,
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Participants

Brianna McHorse	Harvard University
Judith Sclafani	Penn State University
Alexis Rojas	Florida Museum of Natural History
Maria Vallejo-Pareja	Smithsonian Tropical Research Institute
Talia Moore	Harvard University
Terry Gates	NC Museum of Natural Sciences/North Carolina State
Jack Oyston	University of Bath
Alexander Florez Rodriguez	University of Copenhagen
Daniel Field	Yale University
Allan Santos	Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro
Megan Whitney	University of Washington
David Wright	Ohio State University
Selina Cole	The Ohio State University
Stewart Edie	University of Chicago
Graham Slater	National Museum of Natural History, The Smithsonian
Samantha Price	University of California-Davis
Lars Schmitz	Keck Graduate Institute (Claremont, CA)
Samantha Hopkins	University of Oregon
Roger Benson	University of Oxford
Daniel Rabosky	University of Michigan
Gene Hunt	Smithsonian Institution
Mariangeles Arce H.	Stony Brook University
Timothy Astrop	University of Bath
Steve Hageman	Appalachian State University
Susanne Cote	University of Calgary
Katie Davis	University of Bath
Matt Davis	Yale University
Fabio Roxo	UNESP
Ian Caldas	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro
Danielle Fraser	Carleton University
Haley Wightman	Brigham Young University
Addison Kemp	University of Texas-Austin
Sora Kim	University of Chicago
Fabio Machado	Universidade de S•o Paulo

NESCent Academy Course: Phylogenetic Analysis Using RevBayes

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=431

Dates: 8/25/2014 - 8/29/2014

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Working Group

Software for bayesian evolutionary analysis by sampling trees

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=191

Dates: 12/4/2013 - 12/6/2013

PI

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University of California-Los Angeles

Participants

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Peter Beerli
Katia Koelle
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Denise KÄ¼hnert
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Remco Bouckaert
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Jeff Thorne
Benjamin D Redelings
Tim Vaughan
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Connor McCoy
Kuangyu Wang
Marc Suchard
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Rega Institute, KU Leuven
Florida State University
Duke University
UC Berkeley and University of Kansas
ETH Zurich
University of California, Berkeley
University of Auckland
NESCent
North Carolina State University
Duke University
Massey University
Harvard University
Fred Hutchinson Cancer Research Center
North Carolina State University
University of California, Los Angeles
University of Connecticut

Learning Evolution from the Fossil Record: K-12 Explorations in Deep Time

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=345

Dates: 1/7/2014 - 1/9/2014

PI

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Olayinka Mohorn-Mintah
Tammy Maldonado
Lisa White
Dena Smith

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Bowling Green State University (Bowling Green, OH)
Bryn Mawr College
University of Illinois-Chicago
University of Colorado-Boulder
University of California-Berkeley
University of Colorado-Boulder

Genetics and Genealogy: Teaching Evolution and Human Diversity to Middle School Students

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=369

Dates: 1/24/2014 - 1/27/2014

PI

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Wallace Sharif
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Duke University
University of Alabama
Spelman College
Fellman Studio
The Pennsylvania State University
NESCent
University of Pennsylvania
James Madison University
Pennsylvania State University
Morehouse College
Harvard University

Trends in the evolution of human viruses

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=404

Dates: 1/27/2014 - 1/29/2014

PI

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Rustom Antia

Emory University

Sarah Cobey

University of Chicago (Chicago, IL)

Katrina Lythgoe

Imperial College

Katia Koelle

Duke University

Trevor Bedford

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Veronika Zarnitsyna

Emory University

A working group to solve problems in model selection and phylogeny in mixed multi-factor meta-analysis

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=314

Dates: 2/6/2014 - 2/10/2014

PI

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Participants

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Wolfgang Viechtbauer
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Marc Lajeunesse
Megan Rua
Peter Zee
Sounak Chakraborty
Elizabeth Housworth
Bala Chaudhary
James Umbanhowar
James Meadow
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University of Mississippi
Maastricht University
University of Montana
Indiana University
University of Toulouse
University of South Florida
University of Mississippi
Stanford University
University of Missouri
Indiana University
Loyola University Chicago
University of North Carolina
University of Oregon
University of Mississippi

Environmental and demographic determinants of natural selection

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=326

Dates: 2/10/2014 - 2/13/2014

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Erik Svensson
Adam Siepielski
Mike Wade
Nina Sletvold
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University of Oxford
University of California
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University of St Andrews
University of Guelph
Case Western Reserve University
University of California
California Polytechnic State University
University of Oxford
University of North Carolina
Lund University
University of San Diego
Indiana University
Uppsala University
University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill

Advancing knowledge of evolutionary and ecological immunology

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=405

Dates: 2/17/2014 - 2/19/2014

PI

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Mike Sith-Jothy
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Shelley Adamo
Greg Demas
Liz Carlton
Charles Nunn

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Universite du Quebec À Montreal
Iowa State University
Iowa State University
Australian National University
University of South Florida
University of Sheffield
Butler University
University of Georgia
Dalhousie University
Indiana University
Indiana University
Duke University

Toward a unified evolutionary theory of decision-making in animals

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=364

Dates: 3/7/2014 - 3/10/2014

PI

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University of Nebraska
University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill
University of Colorado
Macquarie University
Cornell University
Dartmouth College
University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill
NESCent
University of Nebraska
Colorado State University
University of Maryland - Baltimore County
Aix-Marseille University
East Carolina University
University of Wisconsin - Milwaukee
University of Colorado-Boulder

Explaining cultural diversity: A new evolutionary synthesis

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=400

Dates: 3/5/2014 - 3/7/2014

PI

Michael Gavin

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Colorado State University

CoPI

Simon Greenhill
Russell Gray
Fiona Jordan

Australian National University
The University of Auckland
University of Bristol

Participants

Mark Pagel	University of Reading
Michael Gavin	Colorado State University
Carol Ember	Yale University
Adrian Bell	University of Utah
Fiona Jordan	University of Bristol
Russell Gray	The University of Auckland
Carlos Botero	North Carolina State University
Claire Bowern	Yale University
Simon Greenhill	Australian National University
Kathryn Kirby	University of Toronto
Robert Lanfear	Australian National University
Bobbi Low	University of Michigan

Advancing genetic diversity research in the Indian and Pacific Oceans

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=402

Dates: 3/17/2014 - 3/21/2014

<u>PI</u>	<u>Institution</u>
Cynthia Riginos	University of Queensland
CoPI	
Rob Toonen	University of Hawai'i at Mānoa
Eric Crandall	Southwest Fisheries Science Center (Santa Cruz, CA)
Participants	
Rob Toonen	University of Hawaii
Cynthia Riginos	University of Queensland
Kim Selkoe	University of California Santa Barbara
Sean Connolly	James Cook University
John Pandolfi	The University of Queensland
Peter Cowman	Australian National University
Elizabeth J Sbrocco	NESCent
Chris Meyer	Smithsonian Institution
Michael Hickerson	City University of New York
Paul Barber	University of California-Los Angeles
Eric Crandall	University of California-Santa Cruz
Mark Hixon	University of Hawaii at Manoa
Harilaos Lessios	Smithsonian Institution
Michael Dawson	University of California-Merced
Eric Trembl	University of Melbourne
Robin Waples	NOAA

Building non-model species genome curation communities

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=377

Dates: 3/24/2014 - 3/28/2014

<u>PI</u>	<u>Institution</u>
Alexie Papanicolaou	Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research
CoPI	
Monica C Munoz-Torres	Smithsonian Institution National Museum of Natural History
Yannick Wurm	Queen Mary, University of London

Participants

Alexie Papanicolaou
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Robert Waterhouse
Jennifer Wortman
Yannick Wurm
Gilbert Smith
Andrew Stewart
Monica C Munoz-Torres
Anurag Priyam
Nassib Nassar
Alex Feltus

Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Or
NESCent
Massachusetts Institute of Technology
BROAD Institute
Queen Mary University of London
University of California
Smithsonian Institution
Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory
Queen Mary University of London
University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill
Clemson University

Linking self-fertilization, dispersal and distribution traits of species: Is Baker's law an exception to the rule?

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=401

Dates: 4/3/2014 - 4/6/2014

PI

Susan Kalisz

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University of Minnesota-Twin Cities
University of Minnesota
West Chester University
University of Calgary
University of Pittsburgh
Monash University
Florida State University
University of San Francisco
Washington State University
Universidad de Granada
University of Pittsburgh
Universiti;½ de Lausanne
Michigan State University

Integrating Evolutionary Models of Human Fertility Change

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=403

Dates: 4/17/2014 - 4/20/2014

PI

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CoPI

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Daniel Hruschka

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Participants

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Daniel Hruschka
Mary Shenk
Mary Towner
David Coall
Alex Bentley
Paul Hooper
Oskar Burger
Kristin Snopkowski
David Lawson
Lisa McAllister

London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine
Arizona State University
University of Missouri (Columbia,MO)
Oklahoma State University
Edith Cowan University
Bristol University
Santa Fe Institute
University of Kent
London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine
University College London
University of California, Santa Barbara (UCSB)

Synthesizing and databasing fossil calibrations: divergence dating and beyond

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=259

Dates: 5/5/2014 - 5/7/2014

PI

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University of Alabama,

Alabama Museum of Natural History,

Participants

James Parham
Daniel Ksepka
Jim Allman
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P. David Polly
Matthew Phillips
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Queensland University of Technology
University of North Carolina-Wilmington
Howard University
Palaeontologia Electronica
University of Nebraska-Lincoln
Rutgers University-Newark
University of Arizona (Tucson,AZ)
University of North Carolina-Wilmington

Trends in the evolution of human viruses

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=404

Dates: 5/6/2014 - 5/8/2014

PI

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Participants

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Pleuni Pennings
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Trevor Bedford
Rosalind Eggo
Sarah Cobey

Stanford University
Imperial College
Emory University
Emory University
Duke University
Stanford University
Catalan Institute of Oncology
Fred Hutchinson Cancer Research Center
The University of Texas at Austin
University of Chicago

Infusing Medical Education with Evolutionary Thinking

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=315

Dates: 5/16/2014 - 5/18/2014

PI
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Participants

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Stephen Stearns	Yale University
Cynthia M Beall	Case Western Reserve University
Joseph L Graves Jr	North Carolina A & T State University
Brandon Hidaka	University of Kansas Medical Center
Chris Reiber	State University of New York-Binghamton
Carol Aschenbrener	Association of American Medical Colleges
Gillian Bentley	Durham University
Randolph Nesse	Arizona State University
Nicole Skursky	New York University School of Medicine
Harvey Fineberg	Institute of Medicine of the National Academies
Robert Alpern	Yale University
Jay B. Labov	National Research Council
Charles Nunn	Duke University

Testing theories for the evolution of genomic imprinting

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=366

Dates: 5/27/2014 - 5/29/2014

PI
Jason Wolf

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Participants

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Yaniv Brandvain	University of Minnesota-Twin Cities
Jeremy Van Cleave	NESCent
Hamish Spencer	University of Otago
Robert Feil	CNRS Institute of Molecular Genetics
Manus Patten	Georgetown University
Rebecca Mosher	University of Arizona
David Haig	Harvard University
Soojin Yi	Georgia Institute of Technology
Laura Ross	University of Edinburgh
Andrew Clark	Cornell University

Advancing knowledge of evolutionary and ecological immunology

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=405

Dates: 6/3/2014 - 6/5/2014

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Participants

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Charles Nunn	Duke University
Kendra Smyth	Duke University
Andrew Stoehr	Butler University
Zofia Prokop	Jagiellonian University

Advancing genetic diversity research in the Indian and Pacific Oceans

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=402

Dates: 7/14/2014 - 7/18/2014

PI

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Libby Liggins	University of Queensland
Marc Kochzius	Vrije Universiteit Brussel
Stephen A Karl	University of Hawaii
Cynthia Riginos	University of Queensland
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Michelle Gaither	Durham University
MIchael Berumen	King Abdullah University of Science and Technology
Eric Crandall	University of California-Santa Cruz
John Deck	University of California-Berkeley
Hawis Madduppa	Bogor Agricultural University
John Horne	University of Algarve
Brian Bowen	University of Hawaii

Building non-model species genome curation communities

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=377

Dates: 7/21/2014 - 7/25/2014

PI

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Participants

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Robert Waterhouse	Massachusetts Institute of Technology
Karen Cranston	NESCent
Monica C Munoz-Torres	Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory
Alex Feltus	Clemson University
Nassib Nassar	University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill

Integrating Evolutionary Models of Human Fertility Change

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=403

Dates: 7/24/2014 - 7/27/2014

<u>PI</u>	<u>Institution</u>
Mary Shenk	University of Missouri (Columbia,MO)

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Rebecca Sear	London School of Hygiene and Tropical
Medicine	
Daniel Hruschka	Arizona State University

Participants

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Rebecca Sear	London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine
Lisa McAllister	University of California, Santa Barbara
David Nolin	Arizona State University
Oskar Burger	University of Kent
Heidi Colleran	University College London
Mary Towner	Oklahoma State University
Alex Bentley	Bristol University
David Coall	Edith Cowan University
Sandra Virgo	London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine
Daniel Hruschka	Arizona State University

The Perils of Being Bipedal: an Evolutionary Perspective on Human Musculoskeletal Disorders

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=316

Dates: 8/12/2014 - 8/14/2014

<u>PI</u>	<u>Institution</u>
Bruce Latimer	Case Western Reserve University

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Participants

Daniel Cooperman	University Hospitals-Cleveland
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Brian Corner	US Army Natick
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Bruce Latimer	Case Western Reserve University
Dana Duren	Wright State University
Richard Drake	Cleveland Clinic
Linda Spurlock	Kent State University
Rachel Caspari	Central Michigan University
Karen Rosenberg	University of Delaware

Explaining cultural diversity: A new evolutionary synthesis

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=400

Dates: 8/11/2014 - 8/14/2014

<u>PI</u>	<u>Institution</u>
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Simon Greenhill	Australian National University
Russell Gray	The University of Auckland

Participants

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Carlos Botero
Fiona Jordan
Bobbi Low
Russell Gray
Stephanie Ng

Colorado State University
Federal University
Australian National University
Yale University
University of Toronto
North Carolina State University
University of Bristol
University of Michigan
The University of Auckland
University of Auckland

Learning Evolution from the Fossil Record: K-12 Explorations in Deep Time

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=345

Dates: 8/17/2014 - 8/20/2014

PI

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Tammy Maldonado
Olayinka Mohorn-Mintah
Roy Plotnick
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University of California-Berkeley
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Bryn Mawr College
University of Colorado-Boulder
University of Illinois-Chicago
University of Illinois-Chicago
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HIP: Hackathons, Interoperability, Phylogenies

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=294

Dates: 9/15/2014 - 9/19/2014

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Institute for Bioscience and Biotechnology Research
NESCent

Linking self-fertilization, dispersal and distribution traits of species: Is Baker's law an exception to the rule?

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=401

Dates: 9/29/2014 - 10/3/2014

PI

Susan Kalisz

Institution

University of Pittsburgh

CoPI

Pierre-Olivier Cheptou
Evolutive
April M Randle

Centre d'Ecologie Fonctionnelle et
Evolutionary Biology
Colorado State University

Participants

April M Randle
Susan Kalisz

Colorado State University
University of Pittsburgh

Integrating Evolutionary Models of Human Fertility Change

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=403

Dates: 10/9/2014 - 10/12/2014

PI

Mary Shenk

Institution

University of Missouri (Columbia,MO)

CoPI

Rebecca Sear
Medicine
Daniel Hruschka

London School of Hygiene and Tropical
Arizona State University

Participants

Mary Shenk
Daniel Hruschka
Rebecca Sear

University of Missouri (Columbia,MO)
Arizona State University
London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine

Advancing knowledge of evolutionary and ecological immunology

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=405

Dates: 10/7/2014 - 10/9/2014

PI

Clint Kelly

Institution

Iowa State University (Ames,IA)

CoPI

Michael Jennions

Australian National University

Participants

Clint Kelly
Michael Jennions

Universite du Quebec Ã Montreal
Australian National University

Toward a unified evolutionary theory of decision-making in animals

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=364

Dates: 10/16/2014 - 10/19/2014

PI

Tamra Mendelson

Institution

University of Maryland - Baltimore County

CoPI

Mark Hauber
Rebecca Safran

Hunter College, City University of New York
University of Colorado Boulder

Participants

Tamra Mendelson
Mark Hauber
Rebecca Safran

University of Maryland - Baltimore County
Hunter College, City University of New York
University of Colorado

Explaining cultural diversity: A new evolutionary synthesis

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=400

Dates: 11/3/2014 - 11/6/2014

PI

Michael Gavin

Institution

Colorado State University

CoPI

Fiona Jordan
Simon Greenhill
Russell Gray

University of Bristol
Australian National University
The University of Auckland

Participants

Michael Gavin

Colorado State University

Appendix G: Publications from NESCent Supported Projects in Year 9

1. Abreu F, Morillo V, Nascimento FF, Werneck C, Cantao ME, et al. (2014) Deciphering unusual uncultured magnetotactic multicellular prokaryotes through genomics. *ISME Journal* 8: 1055-1068. [10.1038/ismej.2013.203](https://doi.org/10.1038/ismej.2013.203).
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3. Bedford T, Suchard MA, Lemey P, Dudas G, Gregory V, et al. (2014) Integrating influenza antigenic dynamics with molecular evolution. *Elife* 3: 2610. [10.7554/eLife.01914](https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.01914).
4. Beger M, Selkoe KA, Trembl E, Barber PH, von der Heyden S, et al. (2014) Evolving coral reef conservation with genetic information. *Bulletin of Marine Science* 90: 159-185. [10.5343/bms.2012.1106](https://doi.org/10.5343/bms.2012.1106).
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11. Doust AN, Lukens L, Olsen KM, Mauro-Herrera M, Meyer A, et al. (2014) Beyond the single gene: How epistasis and gene-by-environment effects influence crop domestication. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 111: 6178-6183. [10.1073/pnas.1308940110](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1308940110).
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44. Smith NA, Clarke JA (2014) Osteological Histology of the Pan-Alcidae (Aves, Charadriiformes): Correlates of Wing-Propelled Diving and Flightlessness. *Anatomical Record-Advances in Integrative Anatomy and Evolutionary Biology* 297: 188-19910.1002/ar.22841.
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Appendix H: Press Coverage of NESCent Science and Activities for Year 9

Catalysis meetings and working groups

Evolutionary ecology of primate life histories (PIs: Strier/Alberts)

Killer whales, grandmas and what men want: Evolutionary biologists consider menopause

August 19, 2013

Science News

Evolutionary origins and development of woody plants (PIs: Groover / Cronk)

In the age of open science, repurposing and reproducing research pose their own challenges

May 12, 2014

Eurekalert

Tempo and mode of plant trait evolution: synthesizing data from extant and extinct taxa (PIs: Cornwell / Zanne / Smith)

Study offers clues to how plants evolved to cope with cold

December 22, 2013

Eurekalert

Researchers create largest evolutionary 'timetree' of land plants to investigate traits that permit survival in cold climates

December 22, 2013

Eurekalert

Three ways plants evolved to stand the cold

December 26, 2013

Futurity

Domestication as an evolutionary phenomenon (PIs: Larson et al.)

Chicken project gets off the ground

May 27, 2014

Nature

History to blame for slow crop taming: Study

May 5, 2014

Eurekalert

Scientists pinpoint the origins of human influence on everything from chickens to chili peppers

April 30, 2014

Public Radio International

Reading human history using ancient chicken DNA and chili peppers

April 26, 2014

Ars Technica

Serving Up the origins of the chicken and chili pepper

April 25, 2014

Science Friday

More questions than answers as mystery of domestication deepens

April 18, 2014

Eurekaalert

Ancient DNA offers clues to how barnyard chickens came to be

April 18, 2014

Eurekaalert

How does cognition evolve? (Pls: Nunn / Hare)

Overriding their animal impulses

April 28, 2014

New York Times

Animals with bigger brains, broader diets have better self control

April 24, 2014

Eurekaalert

Animals with bigger brains have more self-control

April 22, 2014

Discovery

This is how you study the evolution of animal intelligence

April 22, 2014

National Geographic

Postdoctoral fellows

Carlos Botero

Biodiversity higher in the tropics, but species more likely to arise at higher latitudes

November 22, 2013

EurekaAlert

Heather Piwowar

Should we ditch the journal impact factor?

Sept. 19, 2013

Science Magazine

Rafael Rubio de Casas

Plants with dormant seeds give rise to more species

April 18, 2014

EurekaAlert

Jennifer Verdolin

Why do we eat Wilbur but not Fido?

August 19, 2014

Slate Magazine

Q&A with Jennifer Verdolin, author of Wild Connection

August 6, 2014

Wired

Social network research may boost prairie dog conservation efforts

July 28, 2014

EurekaAlert

What animals tell us about love and relationships

July 22, 2014

WUNC

[Recent books of note](#)

July 19, 2014

The Toronto Star

[Capsule Reviews](#)

July 1, 2014

The Scientist

Wild Connection: What animal mating and courtship tell us about human relationships

June 25, 2014
Eurekalert

Personality test finds some mouse lemurs shy, others bold

June 18, 2013
Eurekalert

Dan Ksepka

Fossils reveal largest airborne bird

August 9, 2014
Science News

Scientist identifies world's biggest-ever flying bird

July 7, 2014
Eurekalert

World's largest flying bird was like nothing alive today

July 7, 2014
Fox News

Extinct bird species had biggest wingspan ever

July 7, 2014
USA Today

Giant bird was able to fly, scientists find

July 7, 2014
The Wall Street Journal

A newly declared species may be the largest flying bird to ever live

July 7, 2014
The Washington Post

Fossil's 21-foot wingspan shows Pelagornis was 'largest flying bird'

July 7, 2014
Los Angeles Times

Ancient bird had wingspan longer than a stretch limousine

July 7, 2014
Science

Biggest-ever flying bird soared with 20-foot wingspan

July 7, 2014
Discovery News

Biggest flying bird ever gets identified from fossil

July 7, 2014

CBC News

Largest ever flying bird -- a prehistoric 'dragon' -- discovered

July 7, 2014

U.S. News & World Report

Wingspan of largest bird in history revealed by new scientific study

July 7, 2014

The Independent

Fossil dug up at airport may be largest flying bird ever found

July 7, 2014

The Guardian

Scientist links fossil to the biggest bird that ever flew

July 7, 2014

NBC News

World's largest flying bird had 24-foot wingspan

July 7, 2014

Discover

World's largest-ever flying bird had huge wingspan, fossil shows

July 7, 2014

Huffington Post

The world's largest flying bird

July 7, 2014

Slate Magazine

The world's largest ever bird revealed: 'Condor' with a 24-FOOT wingspan soared across the skies 28 million years ago

July 7, 2014

Daily Mail

Largest flying bird ever?

July 7, 2014

Scientific American

Fossil soaring bird had huge wingspan

July 7, 2014

Boston Herald

Biggest flying seabird had 21-foot wingspan, scientists say

July 7, 2014

National Geographic

Biggest ever flying bird and the beast that dwarfed it

July 7, 2014

New Scientist

Biggest flying bird ever: how did it get off the ground?

July 7, 2014

The Christian Science Monitor

Discovery of the biggest bird that ever flew rewrites our planet's histories and mysteries

July 8, 2014

Newsweek

Sabbatical Scholars

Sarah Zehr

Nearly 50 years of lemur data now available online

July 23, 2014

Eurekaalert

We'll never be able to collect data this in-depth on lemurs ever again

July 28, 2014

io9

The lives of lemurs, uploaded to the web

July 28, 2014

BBC News

NESCent programs, leadership and staff

Craig McClain

Sunken logs create new worlds for seafloor animals

April 9, 2014

Eurekaalert

Counting calories in the fossil record

March 25, 2014
Eurekalert

The marine creatures that only live on land plants
April 8, 2014
National Geographic

Evolution 2014

Thousands of scientists heading to Raleigh for Evolution 2014 conference
June 19, 2014
Triangle Business Journal

Evolution experts convene at Raleigh Convention Center
June 19, 2014
News & Observer

Dryad

Scientists who share data publicly receive more citations
October 1, 2013
Eurekalert

Data-sharing: everything on display
August 7, 2013
Nature

A safety net for scientific data
January 2014
American Scientist

Darwin Day Roadshow

Hundreds of high school students learn about science at Darwin Day Roadshow
Feb. 22, 2014
Montgomery Advertiser

Appendix I: Active Projects in Year 10

Name	Institution	Project Title	Start Date	End Date
Catalysis Meeting				
Nina G Jablonski Mark Shriver Henry Gates	NESCent Pennsylvania State University Harvard University	Using Genetics and Genealogy to Teach Evolution and Human Diversity	1/3/12	12/31/13
Michael Whitlock Matthew Hahn Victoria Sork	University of British Columbia Indiana University UCLA	SimBank: Planning population genetic simulations to test statistical genetics software	11/15/13	11/30/14
Marymegan Daly H. Lisle Gibbs	Ohio State University Ohio State University	Integrating Organismal and Applied Perspectives on Animal Venom Diversity	11/15/13	11/30/14
Benjamin Dainat Jay D. Evans Philipp Engel Joachim De Miranda	Swiss Bee Research Centre - Agroscope Yale University Honeybee Research Group Sveriges lantbruksuniversitet Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences	BeeBiome:Omic approaches for understanding bee-microbe relationships	11/15/13	11/30/14
Caren Cooper Clinton D Francis Jesse Barber	Cornell Lab of Ornithology NESCent Boise State University	Anthropogenic Sensory Stimuli as Drivers of Evolution: A conceptual synthesis and roadmap for an integrated citizen-science research network	11/15/13	11/30/14
Sally Archibald Caroline Lehmann	Council for Scientific and Industrial Research University of Edinburgh	The co-evolution of plants and fire and consequences for the Earth system	11/15/13	11/30/14
Amy Balanoff Daniel Ksepka N. Adam Smith	Stony Brook University NESCent NESCent	A Deeper Look into the Avian Brain: Using Modern Imaging to Unlock Ancient Endocasts	3/17/14	11/30/14
Elena Litchman Thomas Schmidt	Michigan State University University of Michigan-Ann Arbor	Evolution and community ecology of host-associated microbiota	3/18/14	11/30/14
Jon Shaw David Weston Merritt Turetsky	Duke University Oak Ridge National Laboratory University of Guelph	Scaling evolution from genomes to ecosystems in peatmosses (Sphagnum)	5/1/14	6/30/15
Cristine Legare John Opfer Andrew Shtulman	The University of Texas at Austin Ohio State University Occidental College	Developing Best Practices for Teaching Evolution in the Social Sciences	5/1/14	6/30/15
Robrert Lanfear Richard Lenski Hanna Kokko Seth Bybee Phill Watts Maren Wellenreuther	Australian National Unversity Michigan State University Australian National University Brigham Young University University of Liverpool Lund University	Realising the full potential of long-term evolution experiments New resources for ancient organisms – enabling dragonfly genomics	3/17/14 3/17/14	2/27/15 2/27/15
Graduate Fellow				
Michael Landis	UC Berkeley	Bayesian model testing of Bergmann's Rule on mammalian biogeography	9/9/13	12/6/13
Heath Blackmon	University of Texas-Arlington	Comprehensive analysis of the rates and patterns of sex chromosome evolution in arthropods	8/22/13	12/10/13
Benjamin Morris	University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill	GeoPhy: integrating geography and phylogenies to support marine biodiversity research.	9/1/13	4/25/14
Christopher Torres	University of North Carolina-Wilmington (Wilmington,NC)	Synthesizing phylogenetic, eco-morphological and fossil data to predict evolutionary rates among flamingos (Phoenicopteridae)	9/1/13	6/1/14
Raunaq Malhotra Mary Poss	Pennsylvania State University (University Park,PA) Pennsylvania State University (University Park,PA)	Methods for reconstructing viral haplotypes and their phylogenies based on DNA sequencing data	1/13/14	5/9/14
Libby Liggins	The University of Queensland	Nestedness and turnover in the genetic diversity of marine species in the Indo-Pacific Ocean	4/23/14	7/31/14
Lomax Boyd	Duke Univeristy	Enhancing the synthesis of new evolutionary models of fertility using new media	8/25/14	11/30/14

Barbara H. Dobrin	University of Arizona	Tracing the Origins of an Endemic Flora, and Extending a Study of Divergence Dating Disparity	5/3/14	5/23/14
Kate Thomas	Duke University	Physical and ecological parameters driving the evolution of bioluminescence	8/15/14	12/31/14
Kara Walker	Duke University	Personality and Transfer Outcomes in Female Chimpanzees at Gombe National Park	9/1/14	11/24/14
David Zonana	University of Colorado at Boulder	How do sexual signals mediate social interactions?: social network theory and the evolution of dynamic signal traits by sexual selection	10/6/14	10/31/14
Alannie-Grace Grant	University of Pittsburgh	Do selfers have greater habitat diversity in their range than outcrossers?	9/15/14	10/4/14
Journalist in Residence				
Mark Moffett	National Museum of Natural History, Smithsonian Institution	Human Identity and the Evolution of Societies	3/1/14	12/24/14
Suhail Yusuf	Dawn Group	Paleostan - or - Fossilstan -- the untold story of fossils from Pakistan	6/19/14	9/17/14
Robert Chaney	Missoulian Newspaper	Wilderness at 50	5/20/14	5/23/14
Long-term Sabbatical				
Aditi Pai	Spelman College	Targeted Sabbaticals for MSI faculty: Biology of women-an evolutionary perspective	8/1/13	1/31/14
Bernd Schierwater	TiHo Hannover	New dimensions of synthesis: from single animal observation to planetary genomics in Placozoa	7/15/13	4/15/14
Jeffrey K Conner	Kellogg Biological Station, Michigan State University	Synthesizing data on natural selection and genetics across multiple scales	9/1/13	5/31/14
Uri Gophna	Tel Aviv University (ISRAEL)	Do microbial immune systems reduce lateral gene transfer in prokaryotic genomes?	8/18/13	8/17/14
Grant Ramsey	University of Notre Dame	The evoText Project	1/1/14	5/31/14
Alexander Weiss	The University of Edinburgh	The Personalities and Life Histories of the Gombe Chimpanzees	12/3/13	12/23/14
Susan Kalisz	University of Pittsburgh	Shedding new light on Baker's Law through synthesis	11/3/13	4/30/14
Bori Igic	University of Illinois at Chicago	The History and Consequences of Self-incompatibility in Flowering Plants	8/15/14	12/15/14
Carola Borries	Stony Brook University	Principles of Primate Life Histories	5/1/14	9/31/2014
Postdoctoral Fellow				
Elizabeth J Sbrocco	NESCent	Exploring environmental correlates of range limits across a marine biodiversity hotspot	1/1/12	11/30/14
N. Adam Smith	NESCent	Evaluating effects of temporal distribution of fossil calibrations on divergence analyses	11/1/11	11/14/14
Kate Hertweck	NESCent	Comparative biology of transposable element proliferation	9/1/11	12/1/14
Courtney L Fitzpatrick	NESCent	Expanded Bateman Gradients: a synthetic refinement of sexual selection theory	1/1/13	12/1/14
Jeremy Van Cleve	NESCent	Mechanistic trade-offs in evolution of microbial sociality, plasticity, virulence	1/7/13	12/1/14
Joshua Martin	NESCent	Quantitative Predictions of RNA Evolution	7/2/12	11/30/14
Daniel Ksepka	NESCent	Large scale patterns of disparity between the fossil record and divergence dating analyses	1/1/13	12/31/14
Fabricia Nascimento	NESCent	The evolutionary dynamics of endogenous retroviruses	1/16/13	12/31/14
Jonathan Lombard	NESCent	Early membrane cellular functions: new insights from phylogenetic comparisons	2/15/13	12/31/14
Short-term Visitor				
Charles Pence	University of Notre Dame	The evoText Project	9/16/13	12/15/13
Vladimir Vershinin	Institute of Plant and Animal Ecology	Longitudinal Study of Amphibian Populations in Urban and Natural Environment	10/1/13	12/17/13
Mary Poss	Pennsylvania State University	Evolutionary dynamics of a recently colonized, transcriptionally active endogenous retrovirus.	10/1/13	4/18/14

Yaniv Brandvain Jon Wilkins Jeremy Van Cleve Francisco Ubeda	UC Davis Ronin Institute NESCent University of London.	Does mother-fetus coevolution lead to coadaptation?	11/7/13	2/16/14
Erica Tennenhouse	University of Toronto	Heritability of body mass in sexually monomorphic animals	1/15/14	3/8/14
Sarah Rolfes	TiHo Hannover, ITZ, Division of Ecology and Evolution	Evolution of the p53-network in Placozoa	1/6/14	4/30/14
Rachel Adams Holly Bik Ashley Bateman James Meadow	University of California-Berkeley University of California Davis University of Oregon University of Oregon	Meta-Analysis of Microbial Datasets from Built Environments	4/15/14	5/15/14
Beaux Berkeley Sarah Zehr	James Madison University Duke Lemur Center	Summarizing a multi-model analysis of biased birth sex ratios in captive prosimians at the DLC	6/15/14	8/1/14
Christina M Caruso	University of Guelph	The strength of phenotypic selection on floral traits	6/20/14	8/18/14
Breana Hall James Mullins	University of Washington-Seattle University of Washington-Seattle	An Improved Web Tool to Assess Recombination	3/15/14	5/14/14
Hafiz Maherali	University of Guelph	Physiological and climate niche consequences of genome duplication in angiosperms	6/20/14	8/18/14
Tamra Mendelson Rebecca Safran Maria R Servedio	University of Maryland - Baltimore County University of Colorado University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill	New Directions in Sexual Selection: A Synthesis in Preparation for a Book	3/1/14	10/15/14
Rob Gysel	UC Davis	Why are Read-Overlap Graphs Computationally Tractable?	7/1/14	8/29/14
Jessica Kissinger	University of Georgia	Tools to Study the Evolution of Host-Pathogen Interactions	8/10/14	10/10/14
Frans Plooi	International Research-institute on Infant Studies	Translation of field notes for developmental study of chimpanzee vocal communication, Part 2: Adults	9/15/14	10/16/14
Emanuele Serrelli	University of Milano Bicocca	What is evolutionary synthesis? The NESCent experience	6/30/14	7/18/14
Yonas Tekle	Spelman College	In Search of the Molecular Signs of Sex in Amoebozoa	9/1/14	10/31/14
Working Group				
Jason Hoeksema	University of Mississippi	A working group to solve problems in model selection and phylogeny in mixed multi-factor meta-analysis	11/2/11	12/31/13
Mark Schwartz Peter T Ellison	New York University School of Medicine Harvard Univeristy	Infusing Medical Education with Evolutionary Thinking	11/4/11	12/5/13
Bruce Latimer Linda Spurlock	Case Western Reserve University Cleveland Museum of Natural History	The Perils of Being Bipedal: an Evolutionary Perspective on Human Musculoskeletal Disorders	11/4/11	12/5/13
Margaret Yacobucci Pedro Marengo Dena Smith Roy Plotnick	Bowling Green State Universit Bryn Mawr College University of Colorado University of Illinois	Learning Evolution from the Fossil Record: K-12 Explorations in Deep Time	6/18/12	7/19/14
Tamra Mendelson Rebecca Safran Mark Hauber	University of Maryland - Baltimore County University of Colorado Boulder Hunter College, City University of New York	Toward a unified evolutionary theory of decision-making in animals	2/1/13	11/30/14
Jason Wolf Hamish Spencer	University of Bath University of Otago	Testing theories for the evolution of genomic imprinting	2/1/13	11/30/14
Nina G Jablonski Mark Shriver Eric Plutzer Catherine Bliss	Pennsylvania State University Pennsylvania State University Pennsylvania State University Brown University	Genetics and Genealogy: Teaching Evolution and Human Diversity to Middle School Students	1/1/13	11/14/14

Alexie Papanicolaou Yannick Wurm Monica C Munoz-Torres	Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation Queen Mary, University of London Smithsonian Institution National Museum of Natural History	Building non-model species genome curation communities	2/3/13	11/30/14
Michael Gavin Simon Greenhill Russell Gray Fiona Jordan	Colorado State University Australian National University The University of Auckland University of Bristol	Explaining cultural diversity: A new evolutionary synthesis	5/1/13	11/15/14
Susan Kalisz April M Randle Pierre-Olivier Cheptou	University of Pittsburgh Colorado State University Centre d'Ecologie Fonctionnelle et Evolutive	Linking self-fertilization, dispersal and distribution traits of species: Is Baker's law an exception to the rule?	5/1/13	11/15/14
Cynthia Riginos Rob Toonen Eric Crandall	University of Queensland University of Hawai'i at Mānoa Southwest Fisheries Science Center (Santa Cruz, CA)	Advancing genetic diversity research in the Indian and Pacific Oceans	5/1/13	11/15/14
Mary Shenk Rebecca Sear Daniel Hruschka	University of Missouri London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine Arizona State University	Integrating Evolutionary Models of Human Fertility Change	5/1/13	11/15/14
Pleuni Pennings Sarah Cobey	Stanford University University of Chicago	Trends in the evolution of human viruses	5/1/13	11/15/14
Clint Kelly Michael Jennions	Iowa State University Australian National University	Advancing knowledge of evolutionary and ecological immunology	5/1/13	11/15/14

Appendix J: Projects Supported In Year 10
(Project Titles Are Hyperlinks)

Catalysis Meeting	
Richard Lenski Hanna Kokko Robert Lanfear	Realising the full potential of long-term evolution experiments (DOI)
N. Adam Smith Daniel Ksepka Amy Balanoff	A Deeper Look into the Avian Brain: Using Modern Imaging to Unlock Ancient Endocasts
Phill Watts Maren Wellenreuther Seth Bybee	New resources for ancient organisms – enabling dragonfly genomics
John Opfer Andrew Shtulman Cristine Legare	Developing Best Practices for Teaching Evolution in the Social Sciences
David Weston Merritt Turetsky Jon Shaw	Scaling evolution from genomes to ecosystems in peatmosses (Sphagnum)
Thomas Schmidt Elena Litchman	Evolution and community ecology of host-associated microbiota
Graduate Fellow	
Mary Shenk Greg Wray Lomax Boyd	Enhancing the synthesis of new evolutionary models of fertility using new media
David Zonana	How do sexual signals mediate social interactions?: social network theory and the evolution of dynamic signal traits by sexual selection
Libby Liggins	Nestedness and turnover in the genetic diversity of marine species in the Indo-Pacific Ocean
Kate Thomas	Physical and ecological parameters driving the evolution of bioluminescence
Alannie-Grace Grant	Do selfers have greater habitat diversity in their range than outcrossers?
Barbara H. Dobrin	Tracing the Origins of an Endemic Flora, and Extending a Study of Divergence Dating Disparity
Anne Pusey Alexander Weiss Kara Walker	Personality and Transfer Outcomes in Female Chimpanzees at Gombe National Park
Journalist in Residence	
Mark Moffett	Human Identity and the Evolution of Societies
Suhail Yusuf	Paleostan - or - Fossilstan -- the untold story of fossils from Pakistan
Robert Chaney	Wilderness at 50
Short-term Visitor	
Rebecca Safran	New Directions in Sexual Selection: A Synthesis in Preparation for a Book
Maria R Servedio Rebecca Safran Tamra Mendelson	New Directions in Sexual Selection: A Synthesis in Preparation for a Book
James Mullins Breana Hall	An Improved Web Tool to Assess Recombination
Christina M Caruso	The strength of phenotypic selection on floral traits
Sarah Zehr Beaux Berkeley	Summarizing a multi-model analysis of biased birth sex ratios in captive prosimians at the DLC

Hafiz Maherali	Physiological and climate niche consequences of genome duplication in angiosperms
Ashley Bateman Holly Bik James Meadow Rachel Adams	Meta-Analysis of Microbial Datasets from Built Environments
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Frans Plooi	Translation of field notes for developmental study of chimpanzee vocal communication, Part 2: Adults
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